

ReDREAM
change your energy

D1.5 Qualitative Research Report on Consumer Engagement and Strategic Framework as a basis for Systems & Service Design

A Consumer engagement methodology

March 2022

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1

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Summary

ReDREAM Project

The energy market is rapidly transforming and so is the role of the consumer. Yesterday's passive consumers are central actors in today's energy markets. As new prosumers, energy markets can benefit from their generation, consumption and storage capabilities. The EU-funded ReDREAM project will enable the effective participation of consumers and prosumers in the energy market. The project will develop a strategy for the creation of a value generation chain based on a revolutionary service-dominant logic in which services are exchanged. The project will foster the demand response tools and energy/non-energy services that enable consumers to participate in the energy market. This will lead to the establishment of a new concept: a connected user-centred energy ecosystem.

Summary of Deliverable

What are the key levers for recruitment and engagement in the pilots?

What articulates a processual model guiding the recruitment, onboarding, and engagement users' trajectory?

How to offer specific recommendations based on context and type of user or user cases?

What are actionable tools for pilot managers?

What are the actionable insights that can be exploited and replicated for users' recruitment and engagement in flexibility markets?

This deliverable represents the outcome of task 1.5 (WP1) representing the consumer engagement project methodology implementation. Drawing from the research conducted in task 1.1 region-specific key motivators and user distinctions have been unveiled, to obtain a more targeted strategy to boost engagement in ReDREAM. The distillation of findings has enriched areas of opportunity for the creation of the engagement strategy and user experience design. The deliverable is structured as follows.

First, a review of academic studies on user's adoption engagement and satisfaction in smart grids is presented. Smart grid systems enable a better match between energy production, especially from renewable sources, and energy demand. Specifically, the review identifies key drivers of recruitment, engagement, and satisfaction among residential, commercial, and industrial consumers, differentiating between individual, social, and contextual factors. This is complemented by a depiction of drivers across stages and across clusters of consumers. This review on smart grids and demand response shows that adoption (or intention to adopt) smart management systems is affected by manifold factors including personal values, value sought, environmental concern, social norms, cultural practices, or social and political acceptance. A fundamental part of this deliverable is the explanation is the "gamification" concept in the engagement methodology is explained for a common understanding of what gamification means in ReDREAM project for users. ReDREAM "gamification" concept where we can differentiate between two types of serious games: reward-based vs. meaningful games.

The review of scientific literature was complemented with a review of the learnings of past pilots in several Countries of the European Union. This allowed gaining knowledge from past projects related with flexibility and engagement in energy communities. The main conclusion of this review is that, although each country has different institutional constraints and contextual differences, common patterns can be unveiled vis-à-vis the strategies to ensure consumers' engagement in electricity markets and, specifically, engagement with flexibility services.

Second, the outline of the three-stage consumer engagement strategy is presented differentiating between recruitment, onboarding and operation or provision of flexibility. The strategy is anchored on three pillars or conditions that need being met throughout the three stages identified. The selection of pillars is based in the insights extracted from the science review and the field research conducted in

Task 1.1. These pillars are (1) value over time; (2) benefits should outweigh costs and (3) trust in the ecosystem.

If the pillars are the foundations of the engagement strategy, the design principles, represented in Figure 9, are the vectors that drive decision making and define how engagement should be approached in the different stages. These design principles are personalisation, visibility, simplicity, discoverability, and managed automation. These principles must be met in each stage and/or design decision of the ecosystem to guarantee consumers participation along with the project. Based on these principles, detailed recruitment, onboarding, and provision strategy is defined.

Third, the recruitment strategy summarizes the key insights obtained from demo partners. It outlines the strategies for recruitment and proposes a model to improve the effectiveness of recruitment. Considering the main objective of the engagement strategy and the design principles, the recruitment strategy comprises four main elements: (1) target (a description and quantification of the population invited to join the project), (2) targeting strategies, (3) communication strategy (comprising both messages and channels that are often interlinked) and (4) KPIs to measure the effectiveness of the other three elements and that serve as the basis for optimizing the recruitment campaigns.

Targeting is the overall approach for recruitment: it can start from motivation to equipment or vice versa. Data collected from demo partners shows that “from eligibility to motivation” is the most effective strategy. To ease this strategy, the requirements for eligibility are spelled out (i.e., equipment, motivation, and location). Tactics to use these three criteria in recruitment are provided. This is complemented with a set of guidelines for crafting messages and choosing channels; with a proposal of analytical and planning tools to enable the recruitment strategies.

Fourth, the adoption strategy comprises guidelines to facilitate and increase satisfaction of users during the onboarding into ReDREAM’s ecosystem. Although onboarding is the shortest stage participants will go through during the entire process, it is a critical stage, as it is in this stage where users adopt the new solution and start adopting the new active role required in flexibility markets. During the recruitment stage, potential participants express their interest to participate in ReDREAM and if they are eligible, they are invited to adopt the solution, but they are not offering their resources yet for flexibility. It is in the onboarding stage where participants match their resources – make them available in the ecosystem-. This matching will determine the subsequent value creation and value distribution among actors. The onboarding journey is defined by eight key steps that participants will experience or go through. The entire onboarding stage should not last more than 15 days so that participants do not lose the momentum – or initial motivational energy-after they have been accepted. The onboarding interfaces should meet the three foundational pillars and the design principles so to minimise the churn rate in this stage. A set of guidelines is also proposed for this purpose.

The final section of this deliverable focuses on the participation stage and proposes the strategy for provision or participation in flexibility services. The ecosystem (task 1.1. and Deliverable 1.1.) was designed to enable consumers’ engagement in this stage. Here, the ecosystem features and their links with dashboard, advisory tool, and challenges are revisited as engagement boosts. Also, the “non-energy services” that include health, comfort, mobility, and gamification are also revisited as drivers of participation. Non-energy services will allow us to enrich the advisory wall and the challenges module with relevant content that adapt to users’ needs. The strategy also averts – and try to neutralize-the three main reasons for disengagement, namely, the perceived hassle, the anticipated anxiety and the perception of limited value or net benefits for consumers. Specific suggestions to minimise these three risks are provided.

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Table of Contents

List of tables	10
List of figures.....	11
Table of key concepts	12
1 Objectives and method	15
2 A review of studies. Users' adoption, engagement, and satisfaction in smart grids pilots	17
2.1 Introduction	17
2.2 Residential consumers' adoption of and engagement with smart management systems ..	19
2.2.1 Individual-level factors explaining adoption	20
2.2.2 Social factors explaining adoption	25
2.2.3 Contextual and institutional factors: a practice lens to the study of energy systems	27
2.2.4 Contextual factors: media and experts' frames	29
2.2.5 Integrating insights: stages and clusters of consumers.....	30
2.3 Industrial and commercial consumers' adoption of demand response	32
2.4 Gamification.....	33
2.5 Learnings from other pilots.....	35
2.5.1 Description of pilots under analysis	35
2.5.2 Findings	36
3 Consumer Engagement Strategy Fundamentals.....	38
3.1 Objective	38
3.2 Pillars and principles	38
3.2.1 Value over time	38
3.2.2 Benefit > Effort	38
3.2.3 Trust in the ecosystem	39
3.2.4 ReDREAM's design principles.....	40
3.3 Engagement Phases for the Demos	40
4 Recruitment strategy	41
4.1 Introduction	41
4.2 Three-fold approach guidelines	41
4.2.1 Guidelines for targeting or overall approach to recruitment.....	43
4.2.2 Guidelines for messages.....	51
4.2.3 Guidelines for channels.....	53

- 4.3 Analytical and planning tools.....54
 - 4.3.1 Decision-making flow chart.....54
 - 4.3.2 Participants’ recruitment journey56
 - 4.3.3 Experiments table58
 - 4.3.4 Initiative’s matrix.....58

- 5 Onboarding strategy 60**
 - 5.1 Introduction60
 - 5.2 Consumers onboarding journey.....60
 - 5.3 ReDREAM principles applied to the onboarding process62
 - 5.3.1 Personalisation.....62
 - 5.3.2 Visibility63
 - 5.3.3 Simplicity64
 - 5.3.4 Discoverability.....64
 - 5.3.5 Managed Automation65
 - 5.4 Guidelines for onboarding process65

- 6 Operation strategy 68**
 - 6.1 Introduction68
 - 6.2 ReDREAM’s principles and technological musts to ensure participation68
 - 6.3 Ecosystem features that foster engagement.....69
 - 6.3.1 Advisory wall70
 - 6.3.2 Challenges70
 - 6.3.3 Progressive functionalities releasement71
 - 6.3.4 Personalization of the user interface71
 - 6.4 Human connection.....72
 - 6.4.1 Consumer support to ensure engagement72
 - 6.4.2 Parallel initiatives and feedback collection72
 - 6.4.3 Role of flex community champions (leaders).....72

- 7 Conclusions 73**

- 8 References 74**

- 9 Appendix 1. Eligibility form 80**

List of Tables

Table 1. Motives for non-use and corresponding demographic profile (Kahma and Matchoss, 2017)	24
Table 2. Cluster of practices, fit with smart grids and solution (Smale et al., 2017)	29
Table 3. Resources missing for small industrial and commercial consumers adapted from Valor et al. (2021)	33
Table 4. List of EU Projects reviewed with description and link	35
Table 5. List of engagement phases	40
Table 6. Articulation of ReDREAM's principles for recruitment	41
Table 7. Technical requirements by type of user	43
Table 8. Archetypes by demo location (summary of key learnings)	44
Table 9. Spaces for some motivation-segmented target groups	46
Table 10. Possible commercial and agro-industrial facilities with eligible equipment	48
Table 11. Assumptions and next steps for residential consumer with eligible equipment	49
Table 12. Equipment spotting techniques	50
Table 13. Strengths and weaknesses of targeting approaches	51
Table 14. Local references to highlight in the onboarding process per demo	62
Table 15. Adaption of onboarding form to the type of user	63
Table 16. Guidelines for the onboarding process	67
Table 17. Ecosystem musts defined by archetype	69
Table 18. Unlocking features during the app using stages	71

List of Figures

Figure 1. ReDREAM ecosystem parts and key concepts	13
Figure 2. Flex community structure and members	14
Figure 3. Demand response strategies	18
Figure 4. A multi-level model of acceptance of energy innovations.	20
Figure 5. Determinants of intention to use smart grids	24
Figure 6 - Summary of individual-level factors driving or hindering adoption of smart energy systems	25
Figure 7. Factors driving adoption, engagement, and satisfaction with smart energy systems	31
Figure 8. Clusters of users according to energy saving practices	31
Figure 9. Template for gamification design: core elements	34
Figure 10. Three pillars for the consumer engagement strategy	39
Figure 11. ReDREAM's Design principles.....	40
Figure 12. Three-fold recruitment strategy approach.....	42
Figure 13. Consumer archetypes based on energy awareness	45
Figure 14. Consumer archetypes based on their relationship with energy	45
Figure 15. Equipment-to-motivation substrategies	47
Figure 16. Target-channel-message decision-making tree.....	55
Figure 17. Example 1. Participant's recruiting journey.....	57
Figure 18. Example 2. Participant's recruiting journey.....	57
Figure 19. Experiment table example of channels	58
Figure 20. Initiative's matrix.....	59
Figure 21. ReDREAM's onboarding journey	61
Figure 22 ReDREAM's ecosystem features and design guidelines.	70
Figure 23. Welcoming screen	80
Figure 24. Type of user	81
Figure 25. Location	81
Figure 26. Technical requirements.....	82
Figure 27. Possible equipment acquisition.....	82
Figure 28. Eligibility confirmation	82
Figure 29. Denial of eligibility	83
Figure 30. Local contact person	83
Figure 31. Personal info.....	84
Figure 32. ReDREAM eligibility form logic flow chart.....	85

Table of Key Concepts

Concept	Definition
ReDREAM Ecosystem	(or ecosystem) Ensemble of hardware (Stemy Devices, Eligible energy equipment) and software assets (services of the platform, platform itself, interfaces, etc) with stakeholders that interact with technology and among them to provide an integrated energy solution.
Stemy Devices	(or devices) Internet of Things based hardware that is installed in the eligible energy equipment of the ReDREAM users and connected to the platform (software). E.g., Smart plug, smart meter or Waddy Box.
Eligible energy equipment	(or equipment) Electric powered energetical apparatus that can be connected and managed by the platform via the Stemy devices. E.g, Hot water cylinder, heat pump or radiator.
User Interfaces	The means by which the users and other participants interact with the ReDREAM platform with a smartphone, tablet or computer or open API (for third party).
Mobile App	(or app) User interface to interact with the ReDREAM ecosystem via a dedicated smartphone app.
Web portal	(or portal) User interface to interact with the ReDREAM ecosystem with the internet browser, especially for computers but also with the smartphone browser.
Platform	Ensemble of ReDREAM services (Demand Response, Energy Efficiency, Advisory Tool, etc.), third-party services (Weather Channel, Energy Markets), and databases that configure the ReDREAM software solution.
Consumer	Person that inhabits a space (house, building, factory, etc.) that has a consumption of energy.
Prosumer	Person that inhabits a space (house, building, factory, etc.) that has a consumption of energy but also generation capacity. Hereinafter, to not constantly make distinctions between consumers and prosumers, we will consider both under the concept of consumers.
Flex community	Group of aggregated users and other participants (managers and service providers) that located in specific geographical area that provide energy flexibility and efficiency to the grid using the ReDREAM ecosystem.
Users	Consumers or prosumers that uses, directly (active users) or indirectly (passive users), the ReDREAM ecosystem and is part of the flex community.
Active user	Participants that are registered into the ReDREAM ecosystem via the Mobile app and/or the Web portal. Active user can have one of these two rules: Administrators – the person that signed the terms and conditions- or Observers – use the interfaces -
Passive user	Participant that is under the influence of the ReDREAM ecosystem (inhabits in a building with managed equipment by the ReDREAM hardware and software) but has no direct interaction nor user account in the ecosystem. E.g., workers of a factory
Administrator user	Active user that has full access to all features and permissions of the ecosystem and also manages other active users.
Observer user	Active user registered in the ecosystem but with limited access to the ecosystem features.
Other Participants	Members of the ReDREAM community that are no consumers but have an active role by managing it (manager) or providing services (installers, customer support)
Manager	Participant with no consumer/prosumer role; rather s/he manages the ecosystem and the ReDREAM community locally overseeing the onboarding of participants and network of installers, etc. E.g., Demo partner

Service provider	Participant that provides services to users, such as customer support or device/equipment installations using the platform to manage it. E.g., authorised installer, Stemy
Consumer Engagement Strategy	Approach to increase the participation of consumers in the energy transition and market through the ReDREAM ecosystem.
Recruitment	First phase of the consumer engagement strategy that aims at identifying eligible consumers to be part of the ReDREAM ecosystem (motivated to participate, in the demo location and with eligible energy equipment).
Onboarding	Second phase of the consumer engagement strategy that aims at onboarding consumer into the ReDREAM platform, installing the devices and triggering a role shift in consumers. This stage begins when the user fills up the info in the web portal and finishes when the devices are installed in the building and users have downloaded and registered in the app .
Operation	Third and last phase of the consumer engagement strategy which aims at enabling participants operate with the ecosystem by managing their energy resources, providing flexibility to the grid, be more energy efficient over time and interacting with the community cocreating value.

Figure 1. ReDREAM ecosystem parts and key concepts

Figure 2. Flex community structure and members

1 Objectives and method

With the social objective of placing the users at the centre of the service system and ensuring their engagement in co-created energy markets, this report deploys a strategy to guide the consumer's recruitment, onboarding, and engagement with the energy ecosystem, and more specifically ReDREAM Energy Ecosystem. The main objectives of this report are specified next.

Objective 1: Identify key levers for recruitment and engagement in the pilots

Objective 2: Articulate a processual model guiding the recruitment, onboarding, and engagement users' trajectory

Objective 3: Offer specific recommendations based on context and type of user or user cases

Objective 4: Provide actionable tools for pilot managers

Objective 5: Provide actionable insights that can be exploited and replicated for users' recruitment and engagement in flexibility markets.

To meet these objectives, it was necessary to draw from task 1.1. where an initial understanding of the context of the four demo locations was obtained, followed by a deeper, more structured qualitative study of users and stakeholders in the four demo locations. Based on the insights emerging from this research, the users' requirements, functionalities and use cases of the ecosystem, and KPIs were outlined. The research also helped unveiled the prototypes of users (user cases), their prevalence across demo locations, and the key levers and brakes for each of them along the journey considered (from recruitment to engagement).

In addition to drawing from this research, the method followed for outlining the strategy combined different techniques in an iterative process. We first reviewed the existing literature on drivers of recruitment, engagement, and satisfaction of users in similar projects (i.e., demand response or flexibility energy markets). More specifically, the review was carried out by searching for papers in Scopus and Web of Science Core Collection, using the search strings: (1) (engagement OR adoption) AND ("smart home" OR "smart grid"); (2) flexibility NEAR energy AND (household OR consumers) and 3. "demand response" NEAR energy NEAR consumers, with no time exclusions and limiting the results to journal and conference papers published in English, French, Italian or Spanish. This review showed that although the drivers of engagement are well-known, the literature remains silent as to drivers of recruiting and onboarding.

This academic review was complemented with a benchmark of past EU Horizon 2020 pilots, with the aim of obtaining insights about past strategies for consumer engagement with energy, and particularly with flexibility. This benchmark supplemented the learnings for the operation or participation stage, but we could not find insights to guide the recruitment and onboarding stages.

Given the limited insights obtained in archival data that could orient the recruiting and onboarding strategies, we opted for two participatory methods with demo partners. The first one consisted of a two-hours online workshops with each Demo partner, with the aim to understand the Demo context and situation related with recruitment, identify their perceived best practices - as learnt in other projects and practices of the organization- and to retake the research insights gathered on the first phase. The workshop helped identify possible recruitment ideas and strategies to apply them on each Demo site.

Second, two participatory, co-creation-based one-hour workshops with demo partners and consortium partners were held in Madrid, during the first face-to-face project meeting in October 2020. The first one was mostly focused on pilot managers. The session was structured as follows. First,

each pilot manager was asked to discuss the attempts done so far (target, messages and channels used), the drivers of success and the reasons for less optimal results or less than expected. After this exposition, an open discussion was moderated among participants to brainstorm potential solutions to the problems identified. The second workshop was tailored to unveil key elements of the messages that should be used in the communication campaigns in recruitment, onboarding, and engagement. Participants were first asked to identify key drivers of these three stages; then, they had to identify key barriers for each of the stages. Drivers and barriers were discussed in the grand group and depicted on a board for all participants. Finally, with these drivers and barriers in mind, participants, grouped in small teams of 3-4 experts, were asked to provide a storytelling or a communication concept that could tap onto the drivers and simultaneously neutralise or overcome the identified barriers. The gathered narratives and solutions, contextualizing on problems faced by Demos Partners, have been used in this document as input to develop a tailored strategy for each demo.

2 A review of studies. Users' adoption, engagement, and satisfaction in smart grids pilots

2.1 Introduction

Energy ecosystems are evolving into smart grids systems. Smart grids present many advantages as they enable a better match between energy production, especially from renewable sources, and energy demand. Smart grids are thus conceived as instrumental in the stabilisation of power grids that become more insecure with greater renewable sourcing and greater penetration of distributed generation resources, such as PV (O'Connell et al., 2014).

A constituting element of smart grids are smart home energy management systems. A smart energy system is an energy system in which renewable energy production, smart meters, and smart plug devices are integrated and coordinated through energy services, active users and enabling technologies (Van der Werff and Steg, 2016).

These systems integrate communication, control and sensing technologies (i.e., smart meters and smart plug-ins) to shape the electricity consumption (Jovanovic et al., 2016), using different inputs of data. Some of these inputs are set by users (e.g., desired indoor temperature, indoor stay hours) and others are fed by other sources in real-time (e.g., outdoor temperature, current or expected hourly generation of electricity, hourly emissions, etc.) With these inputs, the system makes the energy decisions on behalf of the household, trying to maintain a level of satisfaction. Usually, some appliances (i.e., lighting, audio/visual and computers) are excluded as they cannot be controlled without significantly impacting consumers' comfort. Others, such as heating, cooking, and washing, can be included in the system.

These systems also allow households to “monitor energy production and use and provide feedback on energy production and use, which can help the user to save money that may increase adoption likelihood” (Noppers et al., 2016: 13). Hence, smart energy systems combine flexibility-enabling and feedback-enabling technologies.

In addition to the technology, smart grids are constituted by demand-side management strategies. These comprise Energy Efficiency strategies (oriented to reduce energy consumption or energy losses via feedback on consumption, information about energy consumption of appliances, and via refurbishment of buildings) and Demand Response programs (“provision of control signals and/or financial incentives to the consumers, aiming to shift their consumption at times of importance, e.g., times of extremely high demand or when grid reliability is jeopardized” (Chatzigeorgiou and Andreu, 2021: 1). A summary of demand response strategies can be found in Error! Reference source not found. (see also Aghaei and Alizadeh, 2013, Paterakis et al., 2017; and Ponds et al., 2018, for a classification based on automatization and tariffs).

Figure 3. Demand response strategies (Parrish et al., 2020)

The deployment of this energy ecosystem demands that actors integrate resources for value co-creation (Darby, 2020). As defined in S-D logic, the resources to be integrated are the so-called operand resources: knowledge, skills, capabilities, and competencies. In this project, operand resources are also relevant, since households need to have electric heating and thermostats, and some of them will need to have PV and EV. Thus, smart energy systems demand that consumers deploy and integrate both material resources (such as heating and cooling systems) and knowledge and skills (e.g., logging on and off the apps, adapting routines to non-peak hours, learning how to reduce energy). Consumers need to be engaged so that they are willing to integrate these resources. Unless consumers overcome the inertia pervasive in energy value networks (Bonnemaizon and Batat, 2011), smart grid systems will not unlock their full potential.

Past studies have shown that consumers may not have these resources (Iliopolus et al., 2019) or are not aware that they have these resources, or if they have, they are not inclined to integrate them in value co-creation processes due to the dominant inertia in the energy value network, trust problems or due to their being moulded in a non-active energy consumer's role (Bonnemaizon and Batat, 2011). The study by Bonnemaizon and Batat (2011) concludes that deregulation of the energy value networks does not lead by itself to a competent consumer: rather, consumers need to learn and appropriate their new role¹. This learning and appropriation demand, inter alia, nurturing cognitive, instrumental and meta-cognitive competencies to be able to integrate resources. Disenfranchisement or the perception that one lacks ability or expertise to use an innovation is a fundamental reason for non-engagement in smart grids (Kahma and Matchoss, 2017).

This fits with the notion of consumer engagement that is the core of EU energy policy (Bertoldi, 2020). Engagement is a multidimensional process that affects the cognition, emotions, and behaviours of users (Brodie et al., 2011). Engagement depends not only on calculative reasons but also on affective commitment and trust (Gangale et al., 2013). An engaged energy consumer is that who adopts new energy technologies and use them to manage their energy consumption/production. Nonetheless, we should not confuse an engaged consumers with ever interacting consumers: engagement in energy may mean allowing the smart home to make decision on behalf of the consumer.

Engagement could be seen as a dynamic process, starting with adoption of smart home technologies, followed by engagement with the devices, and the subsequent (dis)satisfaction that will eventually ensure that the consumer maintains (abandons) the engagement in the long term. Resource integration depends first on acceptance of energy innovations and second on willingness to engage with the technology and actors in the value network to co-create value.

To understand past research on adoption, engagement and satisfaction, this section summarizes existing scholarship on different related sub-themes. First, it reviews existing studies on adoption of smart homes and smart grids and engagement in smart grids. It presents studies found in the databases Scopus and Web of Science using the search strings: (1) (engagement OR adoption) AND (“smart home” OR “smart grid”); (2) flexibility NEAR energy AND (household OR consumers) and 3. “demand response” NEAR energy NEAR consumers.

This review showed that only few factors have been object of attention and the same findings are reinstated in different studies. To illustrate, there are scant studies that address the role of emotions in adoption/engagement (Del Río et al., 2021 being an exception) or the influence of social factors on adoption/engagement. For instance, the role of stereotypes (including self-stereotypes) or place attachment has not been studied. Thus, this initial review will need to be complemented with an understanding of community-based strategies, energy communities, use of social networks in energy demonstrations and place attachment as a source of value or input in feedback interventions. A complementary review was then conducted to summarize the feedback-based mechanisms and their influence on energy saving behaviours. This is offered in a separate paper (already published) and two presentations. These reviews are complemented with a brief overview summarizing the results of energy-related interventions based on gamification that will serve both to present the psychological underpinnings of this type of intervention and to benchmark key features of successful games in energy demonstrations.

2.2 Residential consumers’ adoption of and engagement with smart management systems

Scant studies have examined consumers’ adoption of smart management systems. Most of the research included in this review has examined use of smart meters which are just a component of these systems. Applying insights from environmental psychology and research on adoption of sustainable innovations, it is plausible to assume that adoption or willingness to adopt smart management systems is affected by multiple factors (Lazowski et al., 2018; Noppers et al., 2016), namely

- Individual-level factors: such as values, value sought, environmental concern, personal norms, identity, perceived behavioural control, perceived sacrifice, or perceived risks. Also, demographic information and lifestyle are relevant to understand adoption of smart energy systems.
- Social-level factors: such as social norms, community practices or peers’ influence.
- Contextual or cultural: energy consumption and active demand depend on the social and cultural practices. Since smart energy systems will work if they fit with these practices, understanding social practices is key to predict adoption (Ghanem et al., 2012; Lazowski et al., 2018). In turn, these practices are shaped by cultural understandings of comfort or what a “home” means.
- Institutional: users’ acceptance of energy innovations is affected by social acceptance, thus establishing the reciprocal influence of market, social and political acceptance of an energy innovation (Press and Arnould, 2009; Upham et al., 2015).

Thus, the literature seems to agree that energy systems adoption depends on multi-level factors. This understanding fits with the idea of “energy cultures” widely used to understand energy demand and energy changes (Stephenson et al., 2015) (Figure 4). The energy culture of a given subject (be it an individual, household or business) is self-directed and therefore the result of the subject’s norms, practices, and material culture, but also affected by external influences. Thus, unless a multi-actor approach is used, individual practices cannot be understood and changed. The following sections explain each of these factors in depth.

Figure 4. A multi-level model of acceptance of energy innovations (Upham et al., 2015).

2.2.1 Individual-level factors explaining adoption

Four groups of individual-level factors seem to influence adoption of smart energy systems: traits, motives, beliefs about the innovation, and trust. These factors are the result of applying three main theories to the study of adoption of and engagement in smart energy systems: technology acceptance models, value-sought models, and value-belief-norm theories (Ellabban and Abu-Rub, 2016).

Results from a Dutch pilot has shown that adoption depends on individual-level factors, so that users with certain traits are more likely to adopt than others. In particular, people with biospheric values, environmental (climate change) awareness and environmental self-identity were more likely to adopt smart energy systems (although recent meta-analyses did not confirm this finding) (Gimpel et al., 2020). Also, individuals with egoistic values were likely to adopt smart systems, albeit for different reasons (potential for diminished costs). However, individuals with hedonic values (more self-indulgent and less likely to self-sacrifice) were less likely to adopt; as smart energy systems demand consumers to adjust their consumption to market signals and this may be perceived as an effortful, time-consuming activity that may jeopardise their comfort, they were less interested in adopting (similarly Pronnan et al. 2017).

Resistance to change is an individual disposition that is negatively associated with adoption of smart energy systems (Perri et al., 2020), as this trait influences negatively attitudes towards smart energy systems.

Research on adoption of innovations has shown that lead users have a set of characteristics that make them more likely to adopt innovations across domains: openness to experience, expertise and experience with innovations, and greater risk tolerance (Matschoss et al., 2014; Parag and Butbul, 2018). Consumers with experience with another energy technology are also more likely to adopt smart grids and to emphasize the advantages over disadvantages (Broman Toft and Thøgersen, 2015). In their study of the differences between pioneers and laggards in smart energy systems Matschoss et al. (2014) found that pioneers had greater scores in expertise and experimentalism and greater sense of competence. In contrast, laggards had greater mistrust in energy companies. The expertise and internet competence has been also found a key driver of adoption in other studies (Nikou, 2019). The perceived competence and self-beliefs are thus fundamental drivers of adoption.

Finally, two individual-level variables (perceived efficacy and personal norm) were also positively related with greater adoption (Noppers et al., 2016). The relationship between values and adoption was mediated by personal norm, problem awareness and perceived efficacy. Other studies also found that perceived efficacy (perception that participation will result in reduced costs or greater environmental gains) influences adoption (Perri et al., 2020).

Regarding motives and consistent with the S-D logic, past research shows that users adopt for different reasons thus reflecting that smart energy systems may create different forms of value for users: economic, experiential, environmental (apparently the least important), identity, and episteme value, as detailed below. Most engagement demonstrations approach consumers emphasizing the potential economic value (Gangale et al., 2013). However, this may not be proven the value obtained, as it is difficult that consumers see a substantial change in their bills as a result of engagement in smart grids (Gangale et al., 2013). Moreover, economic value is not the main predictor of adoption (Spence et al., 2015). Nonetheless, during deployment of demand-side management systems, households tend to react more to price signals than environmental signals (Lazowski et al., 2018; Nilsson et al., 2018). Thus, value sought may change from the adoption to engagement stages.

Noppers et al. (2016) defended that energy services may provide different forms of value to consumers. If this is the case, then, consumers will evaluate differently the attributes corresponding to these forms of value. In their study, users who rated more favourably the instrumental, environmental, and symbolic attributes of smart energy systems, were more likely to adopt (Noppers et al., 2016); notwithstanding, the differences between adopters and non-adopters were explained only for the different importance attached to symbolic attributes. Symbolic attributes were in this study a composite of identity and status value. Similar results were obtained by authors in a study of adoption of electric vehicles (Noppers et al., 2015) and in a study of adoption of smart home management systems (Kowalski and Matusiak, 2019) where status-seeking was a fundamental motive for adoption. Mamonov and Kourfaris (2020) coined the term “techno-coolness” as an overarching construct encompassing the motives of intended users of smart thermostats: their motive was to have a home modern and futuristic, an identity of being technologically advanced and fun to use.

A review of demonstrations shows that other experiential motives such as having fun or taking part in the experiment, or pride in the neighbourhood may be also reasons to take part in smart energy systems (Parrish et al., 2020).

Other studies reinforce the insight that financial incentives may not be the primary motive for engaging in smart energy systems (Ghanem et al., 2012); rather, comfort, environmental concerns, or the idea of living with less resources or make a more efficient use of existing resources are important motivators for adoption, although users do not report more engagement with devices using environmental appeals (i.e., carbon footprint reduction). A study of online reviews of smart thermostats confirms that comfort is the main source of value for users, as they seldom discuss cost savings or environmental gains in the reviews (Koupaei et al., 2020). Different forms of value sought may also impinge on actual energy consumption and energy shift to non-peak hours. A study of Finnish households found that consumers that sought comfort above other forms of value increased their consumption in peak hours, compared to consumers seeking environmental value (Tuomela et al., 2021).

This insight contrasts with the evidence that most demand-response strategies are based on price incentives (Herter et al., 2013; Parrish et al., 2020). However, as said above, actual participation may

not bring billing reductions or reductions in energy consumption, financial motives may not be realized (Kowalski and Matusiak, 2019; Parrish et al., 2020) which would then attenuate trust in the system.

A study of early adopters emphasised another form of value that can be relevant to explain adoption: episteme value or the need to understand how new devices or innovations work or to understand their own energy consumption (Kowalski and Matusiak, 2019; Matschoss et al., 2014). Indeed, participants in smart grid demonstrations acknowledge having experienced this form of value: understanding their energy culture or the relationship between their practices and their consumption was a fundamental benefit from participation (Lazowski et al., 2018).

Finally, adoption is also affected by the specific users' beliefs of the smart home system. The greater the perceived ease of use and usefulness of the system, the greater the intention to adopt. Similarly, the more the perceived trialability and compatibility the greater the intention to adopt (Nikou, 2019). Also, the knowledge of benefits improves the attitude towards smart energy systems (Perri et al., 2020). In contrast, feelings of helplessness regarding energy or limited locus of control reduces intention to take on a more active role (Sweeney et al., 2013). A recent meta-analysis only found two predictors of intention to adopt: attitudes towards smart grid and expected performance (Gimpel et al., 2020). Control over the system seems an important driver of engagement: an experimental study showed that when households perceived less control over their appliances, engagement dropped (Moser, 2017).

Trust is an important belief for adoption. Trust is multi-dimensional as users must trust the system, but also the recruiting organisation. Indeed, past studies show that acceptance depends on trust in the actors responsible for the technology and the more an actor is trusted, the easier the acceptance (Gangale et al. 2013). Mistrust in energy firms is widespread (Gangale et al., 2013) and this may present a barrier if these are perceived as the recruiting or interested actors in users' adoption. Thus, resorting to trusted parties (i.e., housing associations, consumer associations or local authorities) has been a successful strategy in other demonstrations (Gangale et al., 2013).

Trust is also multi-faceted: users must both trust the integrity and competence of the actor being the resource integrator in the value network (Liu et al., 2020). Competence-based trust is defined as "the extent to which responsible agents are perceived to have the relevant knowledge and expertise to implement and manage a renewable energy project". Integrity-based trust is defined as "the extent to which responsible agents are perceived to be honest and transparent about their activities and are concerned with public interests". Both dimensions seem to operate separately: integrity perceptions increase acceptability of renewable energy adoption, whereas competence perceptions only affect positively if integrity perceptions are low (and only in China).

Data privacy concerns led to public outcries following smart grid deployment in several countries (Mah et al., 2016), thus showing that this may be a major barrier for adoption: users do not want to share their data, or only they will be willing if they have trust in the use of this data (Cannizaro et al., 2020; Spence et al., 2015). Beyond privacy risks, the most studied type of risks, individuals also have concerns about cyber security, performance of smart home technologies, dependence on technology and subsequent vulnerability among others (see a review in Iten et al., 2021).

Appropriate communication during recruitment, clarification and management of expectations and expected benefits and costs are fundamental to ensure trust (Park et al., 2017). Similarly, communication is necessary during deployment so that participating households need a person to discuss questions with, dealing with problems before they escalate and clear communication and accountability are fundamental to maintain trust during the demonstration (Gangale et al., 2013; Parrish et al., 2020). A recent study (Darby, 2020) pointed to connectivity problems during deployment as one of the main reasons of mistrust. The project needed phone service lines to solve doubts and fix technological issues. Additionally, the use of "care champions" proved fundamental to create trust: these were well-informed individuals, trusted and valued by participants, that spoke in non-technical languages and could assist in ways that technicians could not. Regarding the appropriate frequency of flexibility inputs, participants in a pilot study reported being ok with daily SMS at the beginning and wishing a less-frequent communication input the subsequent weeks, once they were familiar with the system. When the demonstrator provided customised reports of their energy consumption, so that they could choose when to receive them, they chose to receive them daily (Alan et al., 2016). This

shows again that individuals want to have control over their participation, including the frequency of messages being sent to them.

Regarding barriers, several studies (Ghanem et al., 2012; Parrish et al., 2020) foreground the users' need to maintain control over the system or override the system if necessary; if they perceive not having control over the system, their intention to adopt reduces. However, after experimenting automatisations, control expectations relaxed especially when consumers were adequately informed of start and end times of automatisations (Parrish et al., 2020). Moreover, many consumers express negative emotions associated with ongoing engagement with the device (Jensen et al., 2016; Jensen, 2018). Although researchers understand that this implies less engagement, I believe that we need to rethink and repropose automatisations as a form of household's engagement: the household is the objective of engagement, not only the inhabitants. We should rethink the actors from whom we expect the engagement and speak of actants' engagement. A flexible automatisations approach following Alper et al. (2015) may be the most promising.

Similarly, perceived costs (especially complexity and time demands) negatively affect the intention to adopt smart home systems (Nikou, 2019). Automatisations reduces these costs but affects negatively sense of control over comfort and billing (Parrish et al., 2020). Other perceived risks in the smart grid concern are the already mentioned data privacy (cyber security threats), physical risks about the electromagnetic radiation of smart meters, or the accuracy and reliability of smart meters/devices – some users did not believe that the smart meter worked after seeing their bills and thought it was the demonstrators' fault (Park et al., 2014). In contrast, if the system provided the right option (in terms of savings) at the beginning, households developed trust and were likely to rely on automatisations (Alan et al., 2016).

Regarding demographics, results are not conclusive (Kahma and Matchoss, 2017; Parrish et al., 2020). It seems that higher income and higher educated households are more likely to adopt. Also, those with "flexibility capital" were more likely to adopt (Fjellså et al., 2021a, 2021b). Pensioners, families without children or working in shifts have more flexibility capital and thus are more likely to adopt (Parrish et al., 2020); however, older users and families with children may have more barriers to shift load as they have greater aspirations to comfort (Lazowski et al., 2018). Jovanovic et al. (2016) proposed five household profiles that may be useful for the archetypes (families with and without children, multiple pensioners, single pensioners, and single non-pensioners). Each has a different pattern of energy usage, and this pattern may affect their intention to adopt and their engagement with smart energy systems.

Abounding on age, a qualitative study examined and compared the experience of older and younger adults with smart monitors (Brown and Markusson, 2019). Older adults were more aware of their energy consumption and demonstrated being socialised into energy saving behaviours. For this, their engagement with the smart meter was minimal, probably because they saw limited usefulness. Also, they evidenced having limited skills and confidence to engage with the device. The device augmented their anticipated anxiety and depression as they foresaw losing control and ended up with dangerously colder homes if they effectively engaged and responded to smart meter messages. They were aware of their overspending, but they also reported being entitled to greater consumption due to health reasons.

Concerning gender, a survey of British consumers showed that perceptions of smart homes was greatly affected by gender (Del Río et al., 2021), so that women, even though were in charge of heating and cleaning routines and were more persuaded of the environmental benefits of these technologies, were less inclined to use smart home technologies, felt less able to successfully manage these technologies and expressed more dread and anxiety towards them. Women widely consider that smart home technologies were for men, who like being "geeks" and prove their masculinity by being in charge of these technologies. Similar findings are reported in other studies (Han et al., 2021).

A meta-analysis of success factors of demand-response strategies also concluded that pilots in urban areas were more likely to succeed those pilots in rural areas (Srivastava et al., 2018).

Other studies have examined intention to adopt smart grids applying the Technology Acceptance Model, with the results that follows (Park et al., 2015). As can be seen in Figure 5, perceived usefulness is the strongest predictor of intention to adopt, followed by perceived ease of use. This confirms the

lay proverb that when there is a will there is a way. This study also demonstrates the need to mitigate anxiety associated with participation.

* p<0.05, ** p<0.01, *** p<0.001 → Supported ---> Not Supported

Figure 5. Determinants of intention to use smart grids (Park et al., 2014)

Non-use is not the absence of intention: it may include active resistance. Thus, we can understand non-use as a multidimensional a construct, reflecting different reasons for non-use. In, their study of Finnish consumers, Kahma and Matchoss (2017) found that disinterest and disenchantment (resistance to computer mediated human interactions) as well as disenfranchisement explained non-use of smart grid services. **Error! Reference source not found.** summarises the reasons for non-use together with the demographic segment that reported it.

Table 1. Motives for non-use and corresponding demographic profile (Kahma and Matchoss, 2017)

Attitudinal components	Segment
Disinterest and disenchantment Disinterest: non-use explained by lack of interest in or ignorance of new technology Disenchantment: non-use explained by reluctant or partial use of technology often explained by nostalgic reasons	Males and older respondents
	Respondents with high education and income
	Respondents living in the countryside and in a detached house
Lagging adoption Temporary non-use that will disappear over time.	The youngest respondents
	Highly educated
	Households with 3+ persons
	Respondents in urban settings
Suspicion of the costs and benefits	Male respondents and younger respondents
	The most educated
	Urban city dwellers

Dependence	Female respondents
	Highly educated
	Respondents with high level of income
Stratificational components	
Disenfranchisement	Respondents with assets (physical and educational) different in terms of non-use attitudes
Non-use explained by lack of physical or cognitive availability	Importance of housing-related factors
Displacement Non-use explained by having someone else in the household or nearby adopt the innovation	Minor impact on (non-)use

Figure 6 - Summary of individual-level factors driving or hindering adoption of smart energy systems

2.2.2 Social factors explaining adoption

Social factors affect energy consumption. Consumers do not live in a social vacuum but are embedded in family relations, peer relations and community relations. Social-based interventions (such as the use of injunctive norms, peer-comparative feedback, community pledges, and so on) have been much used to trigger energy conservation (Delmas et al., 2013; Zangheri et al., 2019); they are not that frequent- or mentioned at all- in demand-response or flexibility interventions or in smart management systems. Nonetheless, the potential of this social-based interventions is evident; as reported in a recent review, 40% of respondents would be more likely to join time-of-use tariffs as part of a group than individually (Šćepanović et al., 2016). Likewise, although social media has been designed as a hybrid of feedback and energy community site, its influence on adoption, engagement or satisfaction has not been reported (Makivierikko et al., 2019).

Past research shows that when individuals are unsure of the benefits/costs of an innovation, they look at their peers and aspirational others to disambiguate. Thus, peers’ discourse and practices, and especially those of the community leaders, could influence the individual’s adoption of smart energy systems. We would expect that the more an individual identifies with a group, the more salient is the

peers' beliefs to form their own; or conversely, if the group identification is low, social norms may be not a driver of individual behaviour (Makivierikko et al., 2019).

Another driver that can potentially influence adoption and engagement with smart grids is place attachment. Place attachment "involves positively experienced bonds, sometimes occurring without awareness, that are developed over time from the behavioural, affective, and cognitive ties between individuals and/or groups and their socio-physical environment" (Brown and Perkins 1992, p. 284, in Liebe and Dobers, 2019). Place attachment has two dimensions: physical and social. The physical dimension of place includes the functional and emotional attachment (the socially constructed meanings to landscape and the relations with an individual's identity); the social dimension comprise the social ties and emotional connection based on personal or cultural connections to the area (van Veelen and Haggett, 2017).

Places are part of our identity (Belk, 1988) so that any benefit/harm to the places we consider part of ourselves are lived as benefit/harm for ourselves. The idea of empathy with natural places also reinforces this idea: empathy with a place is a fundamental antecedent of sustainable behaviour (Brown et al., 2019).

Studies on energy infrastructure have long shown that place attachment is a fundamental driver of acceptance of or rejection to energy community developments (Devine-Wright, 2009). Place attachment can be a driver if a given intervention is seen as enhancing place distinctiveness, social ties, continuity, and self-efficacy. Although place attachment has not been used in studies of smart grids, it has been found a predictor of acceptance of energy related innovations, such as hydrogen (Scott and Powells, 2020) or nuclear power (Wang et al., 2020) or time-hour tariffs (Parag, 2020). Yet, other studies have found that place attachment did not affect adoption in biogas plants (Dobers, 2019) or that place attachment was a predictor of protesting against renewable installations (Devine-Wright, 2009; Liebe and Dobers, 2019).

Probably these differences depend on whether the individual and community perceive that the innovation brings benefits to the local area (Stephanides et al., 2019). Indeed, we can adopt a wider lens to understand our "homes" expanding it to include our building, our neighbourhood, and our village: place attachment can be predicated at different spatial scales, from home to block to neighbourhood to city. Moreover, our attachment to places at different scales may induce different responses towards an intervention: depending on whereas attachment to the village or to the nation is primed, individuals may shift their views about energy infrastructure deployment (Devine-Wright and Batel, 2017): global place attachment was associated with more favourable views of smart grid integration than was local place attachment.

Place attachment not only affects individuals' attitudes and behaviour towards energy-related projects; it is a fundamental notion to understand community energy projects or energy communities, since place attachment is the driver and the context where such projects develop. Community place attachment can be defined as "mutual emotional bonds to home and community, shared place meanings, experiences and knowledge, and collective behaviours towards community planning, protection and improvement" (Süsser et al., 2017). Thus, place could be envisaged as a reservoir of resources to be identified and integrated in value co-creation process. Indeed, past studies have shown that energy entrepreneurs tap onto these place-related resources to initiate and transform the energy cultures of a given place (Süsser et al., 2017).

Conversely, communities' matter when defining the perceived risk of a technology. An individual could reject an innovation not because she does not see value for herself, but because she does not see value for the place where it will be implemented and towards, she feels emotionally bonded (Boyd and Pavaglio, 2015). Thus, we need to understand community perceptions of risks and for this, we need to identify the "the local characteristics that define collective life in a locality, including how people communicate and relate to one another to modify or uphold local culture" (5).

2.2.3 Contextual and institutional factors: a practice lens to the study of energy systems

Motives or attitudes are not well predictor of energy outputs (Ghanem et al., 2012). Research has consistently found wide differences in energy usage among households that cannot be predicted by individual-level factors, outdoor temperature or building settings (Hyysalo et al., 2013). Likewise, there are wide differences in responses to demand-side strategies that cannot be explained by attitudes or demographics or prices (Nilsson et al., 2018). Energy demand seems to be very inelastic to time-of-use rates, and only low-income household seems to adjust their demand to prices (Gyamfi et al., 2013; Matschoss et al., 2014). Other individual-level factors that may explain this variation is the limited knowledge of energy or the time costs associated with the use of smart energy systems (Gyamfi et al., 2013). To overcome the knowledge barrier, past approaches have used feedback as the main intervention to enhance the users' engagement. A separate review of studies on feedback can be found in Valor et al. (2019).

Nonetheless, these studies show that although feedback may be valuable is not enough to bring about changes, as we need to account for the social and cultural influences on energy use (Gangale et al., 2013). Or said otherwise, energy practices are shaped by contexts. Motivating individuals may not be an effective strategy if contexts curtail acting on these motives. Thus, unless contexts in which energy practices are embedded change, change will not occur (Šćepanović et al., 2017). Contexts are comprised of four factors: physical (type of climate or type of building), socio-demographic (family composition and size, local community, trust levels), cultural (lifestyles or aesthetics norms), and political and institutional factors (regulation and policy). As they show in their meta-review (Šćepanović et al., 2017), these four elements of contexts influence the success of the interventions aimed at changing energy practices, positively and negatively. The implication of their study is that we need to study individuals and their contexts. Paraphrasing Ortega y Gasset "I am myself and my context, and if I do not save my context, I do not save myself".

One way of examining the influence of context is the study of household practices: the more the household practices (e.g., laundry, cooking, cleaning) fit with the smart management system, the greater the users' engagement. Understanding the household practices seems thus fundamental to understand how users engage with smart energy systems.

Energy is invisible for users: it is only valued to the extent that it allows performing a set of practices or personal projects. Also, the amount of energy consumed depends on how these practices are performed: how appliances are used, when and for what. Thus, understanding these routines where energy is embedded will allow for a better understanding of how and why consumers engage with energy and more specifically with smart energy systems. Moreover, to understand trends and patterns in energy demand we need to understand "how social practices develop, change and intersect" (Shove and Walker, 2014).

Practices are "everyday activities, such as cooking or doing the laundry, which are recognised and linked to interdependent activities and replicated through space and time" (Ghanem et al., 2012: 688). These practices reflect the cultural setting of a user, so that some of the practices are simultaneously similar to other users' practices and uniquely performed. Practices has three elements: "(a) the materials or technologies that facilitate different activities, (b) the meanings associated with the activities and technologies, and (c) the knowledge (or know-how) needed in order to undertake these activities" (Ghanem et al., 2012: 688).

Practices may be fundamental to explain why some households adopt smart management systems, but they seem more appropriate to explain engagement with the system once adopted. Thus, we provide next a sketch of the insights from these studies.

Routines are key for providing a secure everyday life, exempting individuals from the overwhelming task of engaging in ongoing decision-making and reducing our ontological insecurity. Practices also reflect our habitus, the social norms associated to a given class that are internalized since childhood and thus taken for granted, and that reflect different access to capitals -economic, social, or cultural- (Gram-Hanssen, 2008). Or in other words, two users do laundry, but the way laundry is done (when it

is done, which washing machine, what temperature, with what products, how it is hung) reproduce or reflect different habitus.

Research has reached a conundrum (Gram-Hanssen, 2008). On the one hand, it is apparent that individuals need to change their practices to save energy and resources. This has proven a difficult endeavour and routines seem more resistant than one could thought. On the other hand, we have witnessed how the introduction of technology has led to a rapid change in practices. This provides opportunities for using technology to change practices. The introduction of a given technology allows for a change in routines, without claiming that this change is the result of a goal-directed or attitude-shaped individual process. Major societal changes are, indeed, associated to the introduction of energy-related technologies: think of the relationship between female emancipation and the introduction of appliances to perform the housework routines.

An approach from practices served to unveil barriers that psychological-oriented literature could not detect. For instance, Gram-Hanssen (2008) found that differences in engagement with smart energy systems depended on the meanings attributed to temperature. For some, low temperature was associated with healthier lifestyle and being active (a high temperature makes you lazy). For others, a high temperature was associated with a nicer and cosier atmosphere, an enjoyable ambience to relax with family and friends, or even the duty of a good host.

Similarly, the thermostat valves were used differently in the same household. For some, it was a simpler way of controlling temperature and left the valve in the same position every day. For others, it was a form of controlling the environment, and turning them on and off even against the decision of another member of the family. Usually, it is the husband who is in charge, but the wife opens the valve for a higher temperature associated with a cosier or homely environment (which can be thought of as a practice of mothering).

This contrasts with lighting. People believe that leaving the lights on is a waste of resources and attribute their energy consumption to leaving lights on. Lighting is a visible use of energy and thus it is easier to gain awareness and centre change around this practice. Compared to temperature, which is more invisible, users are more prone to switch off lights in the belief that this will reduce the bill. However, the influence of lighting on billing is negligible. Similarly, people adjust their laundry practices to their environmental concerns by focusing on the type of detergent used or the temperature set, but not on the amount of loads they do. Once a piece of clothing leaves the wardrobe it only enters it after going through the washing machine, be it necessary or not. This is a deeply embedded routine, associated with hygiene practices and seldom questioned, despite that the impact of laundry depends heavily on the loads rather than the load temperature.

Other practice-based studies (Fjellså et al., 2021a, 2021b) have shown that some practices fit more easily with demand-response strategies or that some consumers are more prone to carry out “flexibility work”. After clustering the practices depending on their structure and potential fit with demand-response, cleaning practices were found to have the greatest fit; however, practices in ambiance regulation, leisure, cooking and eating, align only with some flexibility instruments (see **Error! Reference source not found.**) (Smale et al., 2017; see also Öhrlund et al., 2019). The fit of practices does not match the actual impact of these practices on energy demand: the shifted laundering and dishwashing impacted little on the aggregate consumer demand curve. These results are consistent with survey studies (Parag and Butbul, 2018) having found that users are more likely to automatise the use of the dishwasher than other appliances. Likewise, Parrish et al. (2020) reviews concludes that engagement with demand response increased for wet appliances that disrupted less family routines. Households were more likely to release control on dishwashers, for instance, because unloading dishwashers in the morning were more easily done than hanging up laundry. Nonetheless, past demonstrations show that the level of disruption is phenomenologically appraised by families.

Table 2. Cluster of practices, fit with smart grids and solution (Smale et al., 2017)

Cluster of practices	Appliances involved	Timing-relevant characteristics	Flexibility potential	Possible instruments & strategies for flexibility
Lighting, heating, and cooling spaces	Lighting, radiators, heat pumps, air-conditioning, other	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Daily and seasonal rhythm; some daily planning •Light and warmth are requisite; timing is inflexible •Frugality and care (conserving energy) 	Medium	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Automated demand response via direct remote control, flexibility contracts
Cooking/eating and leisure activities	ICT, Audio/video, kitchen appliances, electric cooking, other	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Comfort and control over timing is important •Time-critical, daily rhythm •Less reflexive practices in relation to energy use 	Low	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Smart refrigeration
Domestic cleaning practices	Dishwasher, washing machine, tumble dryer, vacuum cleaning, ironing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Frequency, care, thoroughness, frugality •Non-time-critical, daily to weekly rhythm •Some level of (weekly) planning 	High	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Dynamic energy pricing incentives

These insights resonate with the idea of energy as an operand resource that is important to the extent that allows to do other work (Shove and Walker, 2014)- Then, researchers should understand what type of work is allowed or performed with energy. A higher temperature or frequent laundry could be seen as the means to perform a better mothering or hosting role.

Fit with practices may explain why consumers are not willing to surrender control in demand-side management programmes. A review (Gyamfi et al., 2013) reported the case of a pilot study where less than half of households used the program mode in which the thermostat uses the schedule previously input by the occupant to control temperature set points. The rest were in Hold mode, which effectively turns the thermostat into a manual thermostat. Although recruited to the pilot, households did not engage with the smart management system. The information provided by ethnographic studies contrasts with that obtained in surveys. For instance, a study in Hong Kong found that the intention to shift load was much greater than the actual behaviour depicted by other studies – around 60% were willing to shift load or prosume - (Mah et al., 2016).

2.2.4 Contextual factors: media and experts' frames

Few studies have addressed other contextual or influences on smart grid adoption. Despite acknowledging that institutional factors have proven to be the best predictor of individual adoption, most studies have examined smart grid adoption as it would depend on individual choice alone (Wolsink, 2012). However, as other authors have defended, smart grid demands an institutional framework, a governance system that ensures fair distribution of costs and benefits, and typification of new energy practices from all actors, not only consumers (Thomas et al., 2020).

Past studies have underlined the fundamental influence of the media in legitimising a market or a technology. To our knowledge, only a paper studied how the media constructed the smart meter in UK (Hielscher and Sovacool, 2018). They found conflicting frames of smart meter in popular press, with four discourses ("empowered consumers", "energy conscious world", "low-carbon grid", and "future smart innovation") frame smart meters as a source of positive social change, whereas five ("hacked and vulnerable grid", "big brother", "costly disaster", "astronomical bills", and "families in turmoil") represent smart meters as negative forces on society. With these frames in the media, it is not surprising that users are confused and perceive data privacy issues and have concerns about the costs.

Another study examined the images depicted by experts in smart energy systems (technology developers) (Skjølsvold and Lindkvist, 2015). The authors found that developers had negative imaginaries of users, depicting them as knowledge deficient and incompetent. Moreover, these imaginaries were performative, so that they were used to validate their views on acceptable modes of technology development. Eventually, their ideals of users' involvement were abandonment as their depictions of users gained root. This points to the need to involve technology developers in research so that their imaginaries of users are closer to reality. Another study examined the compatibility of the designers' and users' logic in demand-response strategies to find that they were not aligned, with also presented problems of performativity (Breukers et al., 2020).

2.2.5 Integrating insights: stages and clusters of consumers

Interpreting past findings from the SDL lens, several key learnings are made.

First, value sought determines adoption and engagement. However, value sought changes from adoption to engagement stages, notably environmental shifts into economic. Recent pilots show that demand response is greater in response to price signals than environmental signals. Similarly, a study on social acceptance of smart energy deployment in New York shows that prior to the roll-out, acceptance was based on environmental gains: the more individuals thought that this would save emissions, the greater the acceptance. However, after the roll-out, acceptance depended on the willingness to take steps to save money and on the perception of procedural fairness (the way they were treated by the utility firm) (Bugden and Stedman, 2021). They found that acceptance decayed along the process, rather than the opposite. Also, some forms of value gain importance at some stages; for instance, episteme value is most important during the early stages of engagement as consumers start interacting with the devices.

Second, perceived value is also dependant on perceived costs. Anticipated anxiety and stress are a major barrier to adoption and engagement. They can be relieved during the engagement phase with problem-focused strategies such as call centres and local champion. Also, benefits must be visualised, and they must compensate the nuisances, notably the time and effort invested.

Comfort and freedom to do other practices are non-negotiable, even pricing signals may not overcome this (Örhlund et al., 2019)

Third, regarding resources non-material resources such as trust are fundamental for smart grids to work. Control over the system attenuates and consumers accept automatised modes if they trust the system. Another fundamental resource is the "flexibility capital", ability to shift demand to off-peak hours. This capital depends on consumers' (both industrial, commercial, or residential) flexibility to change routines. If they cannot, they are less likely to adopt or to engage with the system. Moreover, they may even feel angry and dissatisfied when the system marked consumption as red, since they were not able to change the routine to reduce consumption (Örhlund et al., 2019).

Figure 7. Factors driving adoption, engagement, and satisfaction with smart energy systems (including demand response)

Also, the previous sections show that a one-size-fits all approach to recruitment and engagement may not work, as value is ideographically appraised by users depending on their contexts and resources. A clustering approach may be a sound approach to establish the users’ archetypes that can serve as a basis for an engagement model. Not many studies have used this approach. Clustering-based studies differ in the variables used to construct the clusters. Frenken et al. (2013) classified users depending on their intention and practices of energy savings, finding five clusters (see Figure 8).

Figure 8. Clusters of users according to energy saving practices (Frenken et al., 2013)

Lawson and Williams (2012, in Stephenson et al. (2015) applied the energy cultures framework to cluster households according to their energy use. Four clusters emerged: the Energy Economical cluster tended to have an inefficient material culture but efficient energy practices; the Energy Easy cluster had relatively energy efficient material culture but not particularly efficient practices; the Energy Efficient scored well on both counts and the Energy Extravagant were inefficient on both counts.

These clusters emphasize motivations and practices as the basis for establishing a typology of consumers but failed to account for their technological readiness and market-mavenism² (Feick and Price, 1987) that, as the review showed, may be also fundamental factors to explain adoption and engagement in smart energy services, such as flexibility provision. We intend to redress this gap, by proposing a classification of consumers based on value sought, relationship with technology and market-mavenism (see D1.1). Moreover, it should be noticed that there are not clusters or taxonomies of factors that explain engagement intensity and/or different paths of engagement with smart energy services. This gap will be redressed in Deliverable 4.6. where a clustering technique based on behavioural data will be applied.

2.3 Industrial and commercial consumers' adoption of demand response

Large industrial consumers have been engaged in demand response and flexibility markets (Siddiquee et al., 2021; Söder et al., 2019). Given the focus of this project on small industrial and commercial consumers, the following paragraphs summarise the drivers and barriers for smart grid adoption (in particular, flexibility services) explored in the literature.

Regarding value, whereas economic gains do not seem to be the main motive for residential consumers, for industrial and commercial consumers the possibility of reducing their energy costs and/or obtaining extra earnings is an important driver, together with the reduction of emissions (often because this reduction improves their value proposition to consumers or because it is a legal imperative) (Ma et al., 2018; Siddiquee et al., 2021). Conversely, limited perceived benefits is a major brake to adoption (Cardoso et al., 2020). Whereas the perceived benefits of energy reduction are clear, the benefits of participating in demand response are less so. First, to participate, industrial and commercial consumers need to deploy some initial investments and given the uncertainty about remuneration and tariffs, it is not clear when they will recover these initial investments. Second, the time and management costs are also high, especially among small industrial and commercial consumers that often do not have dedicated personnel to deal with energy matters and are less able to manage complex energy projects that do not fully understand (Cardoso et al., 2020). Third, consumers anticipate costs associated with disrupted managerial operations that necessarily need to adapt in order to provide flexibility to the system. Cardoso et al.'s review (and studies on small industrial and commercial consumers, e.g., Söder et al., 2019) shows that commercial consumers report similar barriers or missing resources as residential consumers.

The following table summarises the resources that industrial and commercial consumers lack and that are necessary for smart grid participation, based on a review of studies (Valor et al., 2021).

² Market mavens are those consumers that aim to participate in marketplace discussions, as they have have information about many kinds of products, places to shop, and other facets of the market, and initiate discussions with and respond to information requests from other consumer. In our context, a market maven is a consumer literate in energy issues that likes to respond to other consumers' questions about energy production and management. This is a differential trait of the participatory archetype, defined in Deliverable 1.1.

Table 3. Resources missing for small industrial and commercial consumers adapted from Valor et al. (2021)

Type of resource missing	Description
Physical	Smart or interruptible equipment (e.g., smart fridges or heat pumps) that can be (de)activated following market demands for flexibility; storage systems or self-production systems.
Knowledge and skills	Personnel with energy expertise that can plan interruptible industrial operations.
Organisational	Interruptible operational designs: operations that can provide energy in the required blocks; resistance from employees; reliable communication structures.
Informational	Research or studies demonstrating the positive outcomes (notably, economic) of providing flexibility to the grid; studies demonstrating the costs involved to prepare for DR; missing a methodology to measure and anticipate the return on the potential investments that consumers should do.
Relational	Missing trustworthy and cooperative relations with energy operators, notably aggregators.

2.4 Gamification

Gamification consists of using “game design elements in non-game contexts and (...) game principles in the design of certain systems to enhance engagement with these systems and make the interaction more motivating” (Lampropoulus et al., 2019). In the energy context, usually serious games are employed. Whereas serious games are fully fledged games, gamification refers to the application of parts of games in a non-game setting (e.g., a mobile phone app designed to track and encourage energy savings, using levels, points, and badges) (Johnson et al., 2017).

In the context of energy, they have been applied mostly to encourage energy savings (Beck et al., 2019) whereas its use for engagement in demand-response strategies has been residual (Lampropoulus et al., 2019).

We can differentiate between two types of serious games: **reward-based vs. meaningful games**. Meaningful games use game design elements, such as “play, exposition, information, engagement and reflection” (Johnson et al. 2017) to enable long-lasting change. Indeed, the reward-based approach has been found to produce short-term changes in behaviours, but the latter, seldom used, should ensure long-term changes. Reward-based games tap onto extrinsic motivation, whereas meaningful games tap on intrinsic motivation. Indeed, when users have intrinsic motivations for energy consumption, associated with environmental or political values, a meaningful approach may be more suitable.

Regardless of the type, games usually have some common elements, namely provision of information, a rewarding system, social connection, a user interface, and performance status (Lampropoulus et al., 2019). Usually, users are self-represented with avatars, there is a narrative context or story guiding the game, there are feedback mechanisms and reputation systems (ranks, levels, points, badges) and a communication system. Games usually encourage competition (with other users or with oneself) (Beck et al., 2019).

Serious games or gamification are interventions usually aiming at (1) increasing awareness of energy consumption and energy environmental impact; (2) changing attitudes towards own consumption, (3) changing habits (Lampropoulus et al., 2019). The engagement with the game is said to enable the attitude change promoted by the game. Whereas the first objective is usually accomplished, the latter two differ widely depending on the characteristics of the game (Johnson et al., 2017). Behaviour changes are limited in time and scope and there are limited spill overs from game to non-game settings (real life) (Lampropoulus et al., 2019). Thus, although the lay belief is usually optimistic about the impact of gamification on energy behaviour change, indeed there is a small body of evidence; most of studies have serious methodological flaws so that the reliability and validity of results should be questioned (Johnson et al., 2017).

One reason for these poor results is the gap between app design and psychology: a recent review of game-based energy apps demonstrated that these apps do not capture or include the behavioural constructs nor are they based on the psychological underpinnings explaining energy-related behavioural change (Beck et al., 2019).

A review of studies (Johnson et al., 2017) emphasizes that competition and social sharing encourages participation and use of games (although its effect on behaviour is unclear); also, the use of points and prizes encouraged participation at initial stages, but challenges were more useful throughout the period. There is limited evidence regarding increased learning about energy consumption.

In sum, the design of the gamification tool should be based on the psychological underpinnings of energy-related behaviour and for this the WP on energy feedback and design could be useful. Understanding the users' motives is again the foundational stage, as goals or challenges, and rewards should be tailored to these motives (Lampropoulus et al., 2019).

To structure the design, the process model depicted in Figure 9 (Alksaif et al., 2018) may provide a valuable template to integrate game-related features with smart-meter information.

Figure 9. Template for gamification design: core elements (Alksaif et al., 2018)

2.5 Learnings from other pilots

2.5.1 Description of pilots under analysis

It is fundamental to build on knowledge already created by past research projects; this generativity is a key strategy for innovation and for maintaining efficiency; also, generativity is part of the agility that ReDREAM seeks in order to improve the users' experience during their participation in flexibility services. Synergies, collaboration, and information sharing between H2020 projects is essential to speed up learning, expertise, and the implementation of improvements in the relationship between users and energy.

In particular, nine projects were selected as they were the most similar to the goals of ReDREAM: Integrid, Platone, GoFlex, s3c, CoordiNet, [IFLEX](#), [HESTIA](#), [SENDER](#), and [ACCEPT](#). The four last cited are also ReDREAM sister projects.

Also, the Joint Research Centre (JRC) and the Bridge initiative from the European Commission and its dedicated publications about consumer energy engagement were analysed in order to gain learnings about consumer participation in energy markets. A brief description of these projects is offered in **Error! Reference source not found.** The aforementioned studies have been carried out in several countries of the European Union; after analysing the findings of these pilots, we observed that, although each country has different institutional constraints and contextual differences, common patterns can be unveiled vis-à-vis the strategies to ensure consumers' engagement in electricity markets and, specifically, in the new flexibility services. These strategies or learnings from past projects are discussed in the next section.

Table 4. List of EU Projects reviewed with description and link

Project	Description	Link
Integrid	InteGrid's vision is to bridge the gap between citizens and technology/solution providers such as utilities, aggregators, manufacturers, and all other agents providing energy services, hence expanding from DSOs distribution and access services to active market facilitation and system optimisation services while ensuring sustainability, security, and quality of supply.	https://integrid-h2020.eu/
Platone	Platone aims at defining new approaches to increase the observability of renewable energy resources and of the less predictable loads while exploiting their flexibility. It develops advanced management platforms to unlock grid flexibility and to realise an open and non-discriminatory market, linking users, aggregators, and operators. The solutions developed in the project will be tested in three European demonstration examples.	https://www.platone-h2020.eu/
GoFlex	GOFLEX innovates, integrates, and demonstrates existing smart-grid technologies enabling the cost-effective use of energy flexibility in distribution grids for regional energy market actors.	https://www.goflex-project.eu/AboutGoflex.html
S3C	The project aims to provide a better understanding of the relationship between the design, implementation and use of particular technology and end user interaction schemes and the promotion of smart energy end user behaviour. In WP1, the fundamental research question underlying the S3C project was formulated as follows: How can active (or 'smart') energy-related behaviour be fostered by active end user engagement strategies in smart grid projects?	http://www.s3c-project.eu/
CoordiNet	The CoordiNet project will help to demonstrate how DSOs and TSOs shall act in a coordinated manner and use the same pool of resources to procure grid services in the most reliable and efficient way through the implementation of large scale "TSO-DSO-Consumer" demonstrations, in cooperation with market participants (and end users).	https://coordinet-project.eu/projects/project

iFlex	The aim of the iFlex project is to empower energy consumers by making it as easy as possible for them to participate in demand response programs, in which they adjust their energy consumption in response to signals or incentives coming from energy actors, such as price signals or bonuses.	https://www.iflex-project.eu/
Hestia	The aim is developing a mix of Technological, Innovative and Social Sciences & Humanities models approaches to improve the management and use of energy by and for residential consumers. HESTIA aims to develop a cost-effective solution for the next-generation demand-side response services by encouraging residential consumers to engage in flexibility sharing and grid balancing. User-personalised services will help lay the foundation for an open marketplace and new grid reality.	https://hestia-eu.com/
Sender	The project will develop energy service applications for proactive demand response (DR), home automation convenience and security mechanisms. By engaging customers in a co-creation process, the project will shift DR from a reactive to a proactive approach. Consumer data will be collected and processed to identify typical consumption patterns, mirror them by digital twins (DTs) based on artificial intelligence technologies and aggregate the DTs' supply/demand characteristics.	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/957755/es
Accept	Accept intends to develop and deliver such a digital toolbox that allows energy communities to offer innovative digital services and access revenue streams that can financially support their functions and secure their sustainability and effectiveness. The ACCEPT framework will be demonstrated and validated in four pilot sites in Greece, the Netherlands, Spain and Switzerland involving more than 3000 people and 750 residences.	https://www.accept-project.eu/

2.5.2 Findings

A common learning of past projects is the need to gain relevance for users and to reduce hassle and time frictions in their relationship with energy. We will monitor the projects that are still ongoing, specifically the sister projects, to learn how they are facing the general consumer engagement challenge. These challenges are generally addressed with communication and automation strategies for users. Gamification also plays an important role in generating interaction and community. In the next section, drivers and barriers about the EU projects are explained, as well as engagement outputs found as engagement is fundamental to engage users as flexibility projects necessarily embed a long-term participation.

Drivers

- Bright Communication is key to gain consumer engagement, from the beginning to the end; clear, relevant, and constant communication will make users understand how they can participate, the benefits and the importance of their actions in the energy market. Besides social networks activity and interaction, webinars, open-source interaction, podcasts, training courses for users, events, blogs, and testimonials are a good point of contact for communicating with consumers. (Bright project)
- Address end users as human beings instead of as points of electricity demand by tailoring the entire project to the everyday life and the social practices of end users. (S3C project). Similarly, other projects emphasize personalisation or adaption of strategy to different types of users (Integrid project).
- The experiences with *gaming* interfaces and *community elements* in the case studies are promising and inspiring, both in terms of engaging end users in the project and in terms of outcomes. Access, gamification, inclusion, and sense of community where some of the main incentives identified in the S3C project as key non-economic incentives to create community and engagement. Users are driven by positive incentives. Projects that did include playful challenges and competitions managed to harvest success. On a micro-level, easily understandable historical usage feedback information and social comparison feedback can be considered a success factor (S3C project). Local life is a context for energy feedback (gamification, younger residents, neighbourhood energy performance set into individual goals, rewards, badges) and as enabler of

social sustainability (self-organisation of neighbours, recommendations, borrowing tools, initiating local projects. Social capital as the feeling of place identity, social cohesion, safety, and trust. Motivational features help to achieve goals (competing was not appealing for everyone) (Integrid project). A sense of community can be a powerful driver to engage end users (S3C project).

- Users' *time management* has an important relationship with automatisisation. When users participating in energy platforms, *micro time (automatisation)* was preferred to be managed by AI; however, macro tasks – or tasks using up more time- were preferred to be managed manually as users feel they have the control over the important tasks (GoFlex project). Consumers need to relate with energy and flexibility projects in a “smooth interaction” meaning reducing stress and friction or the sense of losing time. Giving personal attention – i.e., listening to participants and helping them on an individual basis, according to their needs and expectations – is an effective way to reinforce active end user engagement. Trust is also of key importance in smart energy trials (Go Flex).
- Users state their need to relate with energy beyond energy and to stay updated with **real-time information** about the surrounding area (**traffic, public transport, news**) as well as household-related tasks, household health and stress monitoring apps (Integrid project).

Barriers

- Explaining and communicating flexibility and the role that users play in the future of the electricity market is hard, since energy concepts are deemed too technique and abstract for the majority of users. Limited trust is a barrier to overcome in all EU analysed energy projects. Without a trusting relation between end users and project managers, on which open and honest discussions can be based, it can be challenging to keep end users committed and engaged in the course of the project (S3C project).
- Personalisation and automatisisation need to address the challenge of data and privacy where users expressed their concern about this topic as energy “lives” in their houses and could extract a high amount of data of their daily life. This barrier is in tension with the expected benefit of automatisisation: being capable to really deliver a personalised experience to gain relevance and relate with users in a long-term. About commercial users, it seems highly unlikely that many residential and commercial end user would accept an automatic system especially for commercial users if it would interrupt the primary process of the company without any notification. (Integrid project)
- One of the challenges regarding gamification is to capture the interest and attention of end users in the long run. Also, data collection through gamification is a rather playful method that is not considered intrusive by the end users (S3C project).
- Regulatory barriers impinge on users' perceptions and business model definitions. Among them, two barriers are repeatedly mentioned, namely uncertainty over roles and responsibilities in new smart grid applications and uncertainty over costs and benefits sharing (JRC project).

3 Consumer Engagement Strategy

Fundamentals

This section briefly introduces the overarching approach of a consumer engagement strategy for energy flexibility pilots. It starts with the objective to accomplish; this objective will be met as long as three conditions are met. These are called pillars and need to remain present and stable among the entire engagement process. The ReDREAM design principles, developed in Deliverable 1.1, are also included as principles or guidelines that should be met to drive every engagement-related decisions. Finally, the strategy is defined by focusing on the three main stages in the users' journey: recruitment, onboarding and operation.

3.1 Objective

The objective of the ReDREAM's consumer engagement strategy is reflected in the main project objective, namely, *to effectively move consumer (as residential, tertiary and agro-industrial) participation to the centre of the energy market through an open and co-creative ecosystem where all stakeholders will actively interact.*

This participation should be sustained on time and implicate the efficient management of their energy and provision of flexibility to the grid by the consumers in order to foster the energy transition.

3.2 Pillars and principles

To effectively move consumer participation and ensure efficient energy management and flexibility provision in time, there are three pillars that will enable and support consumer engagement. Those pillars are critical, so that if any of them is transgressed or not respected, users' engagement is jeopardised (Figure 10). The selection of the pillars is based in the insights extracted from section 2. A review of studies. Users' adoption, engagement, and satisfaction in smart grids pilots, and the field research conducted in Task 1.1.

3.2.1 Value over time

This pillar is based in SD-Logic explained in Deliverable 1.1 and refers to value creation. Users need to perceive value creation from the very beginning to maintain their participation. This perceived value should match the value sought according to the consumer archetypes defined in Deliverable 1.1, economic, environmental, and community value.

The value sought can change in time, so the engagement strategies should adapt to ensure the desired value is still delivered. If users stop perceiving that value is being created for them, it is very likely that they will disengage, which could even lead to abandonment. This would have negative repercussions in the form of lost flexibility provision and efficient management of energy.

3.2.2 Benefit > Effort

The second pillar is also based in S-DL and reflects the fundamental notion of resource integration and value exchange. Participation demands an amount of effort from consumers; however, users are not used to being active actors in energy markets or to be proactive. Energy is passively consumed and taken for granted. For residential, tertiary or small-to medium agro-industrial making such effort is understood as "hassle", which refers to of economic payment or time consumption related to an issue or non-desired interaction (payment management, mandatory maintenance, operations, urgent repairs, etc.)

Therefore, the perception of effort-as-hassle should be avoided. To maintain perceived value and willingness to adopt, effort should be compensated so that users perceive a net benefit. Benefits can be of different kinds, depending on the value sought; benefit can be visualised as a relevant saving in

the bill, a considerable reduction in CO² emissions, or gains for the neighbourhood. Every effort required should be worthy, that is, accompanied with description that such effort will produce.

To maintain the project viability and sustainability in time, it is fundamental that consumers nurture a willingness to pay to maintain the smart energy services provided, enabled by the installation of smart devices. Their willingness to pay would be affected by their experience in the project and the perceived benefits obtained (Valor et al., 2021).

3.2.3 Trust in the ecosystem

As shown in past studies, if users do not trust the solution (technology) or the service provider (e.g., aggregator or technology provider) or the energy community, their intention to adopt is lessened. Engagement depends not only on calculative reasons but also on affective commitment and trust (Gangale et al., 2013).

Trust should be built from the first interactions and strengthen during the relationship. Each dimension, layer or element in the ecosystem should reinforce trust perceptions. Trust breaches, be them related to data management, devices, pilot managers or reliability of the software can automatically lead to termination of the participation and, even, contract termination.

Figure 10. Three pillars for the consumer engagement strategy

3.2.4 ReDREAM's design principles

The pillars act as the foundational elements of the engagement strategy. The design principles explained in this section (Figure 11) should be regarded as the vectors that drive decision making and define how engagement should be approached in the different stages. This section offers a general description of the design principles. These principles orient the strategy in each of the stages and thus are further expanded in the corresponding sections.

Figure 11. ReDREAM's Design principles

Personalisation: every interaction should be oriented considering the consumer archetype and value sought in order to foster engagement.

Visibility: consumer should always know where they are, which are the next steps and the purposes of every interaction or information requested.

Simplicity: less is more; include only what is essential for users so that the engagement process is smooth and do not overwhelm them with complexity and hassle.

Discoverability: consider the engagement process as a journey where consumers learn new concepts and implications of energy and help them to digest all the

Managed automation: always bet on the maximum automation possible the users and recruiters, but still manage to make users feel and have the control whenever they like.

3.3 Engagement Phases for the Demos

Three stages have been differentiated in the engagement process. In each stage, the type of interaction and value exchange will differ. With this division, consumer engagement strategies will be more focused on the needs of all the actors and have a dedicated and tailored approach that will be developed in the following sections of this document and structured in **Error! Reference source not found..**

Table 5. List of engagement phases

Section	Engagement phase	Strategy defines
4	Recruitment	How consumers are identified, engaged, and invited to participate into ReDREAM's ecosystem.
5	Onboarding	How eligible consumers are engaged during the onboarding process and motivated to match their resources into ReDREAM's ecosystem.
6	Participation	How consumers (hereafter participants) are enticed to use the ecosystem to efficiently manage their energy consumption/production and to provide flexibility to the grid, thus co-creating value.

4 Recruitment strategy

4.1 Introduction

This section focuses on the first phase of the engagement methodology: recruitment. It summarises the key insights obtained during the study of partners and outlines the suggested model for improving the effectiveness of recruitment. In March and April 2021, a research survey programme was undertaken with demo partners to (1) deliver the results of the in-depth examination of users; (2) better understand their initial recruitment plan, their resources, and challenges in the process; and (3) establish a roadmap for defining the strategy.

In a second round, a first engagement (including recruitment) strategy was presented and co-designed on a two-hour workshop where the recruitment part was again co-created with each Demo partner towards enhancing their recruitment process as a part of a global engagement strategy.

Considering the main objective of the engagement strategy and the design principles, a specific engagement strategy has been developed for recruitment. Two possible approaches for recruitment are suggested considering eligibility or motivation as starting points depending on the circumstances of the targeted consumers. Regardless of the targeting approach, the recruitment strategy should be crafted and implemented following a three-fold framework comprising targets, messages and channels needed to recruit participants.

ReDREAM's design principles should orient the relationship between demo partners, aggregators, and participants. **Error! Reference source not found.** describes how these principles should be applied so that they orient the recruitment strategy.

Table 6. Articulation of ReDREAM's principles for recruitment

Principle	Articulation	Specific actions
Personalisation	Archetypes should drive every decision	Messages per archetypes Contextualised messages
Visibility	Be transparent, but choose wisely when to tell what	Highlight R&I UE project Reinforce impact possibilities Explain benefits and implications Manage expectations (regarding impact, data and tech)
Simplicity	It's not how much you do, but how precise you do it	Less initiatives but more precise Simple and understandable language
Discoverability	The transformational journey starts here	Educational process Create self-awareness
Managed Automation	Put your effort in the 20% that matters to get 80% results	Use as automated options as possible to inform (diverge) Focus on personal connections to explain and convince (converge)

4.2 Three-fold approach guidelines

Any recruitment strategy comprises four main elements: (1) target (a description and quantification of the population invited to join the project), (2) targeting strategies, (3) communication strategy

(comprising both messages and channels that are often interlinked) and (4) KPIs to measure the effectiveness of the other three elements and that serve as the basis for optimizing the campaign

Regarding the target, the concentric circles depict the three conditions that participants in Demos should meet. Regarding the message, we emphasise that appeals should be targeted to previous knowledge of targets. If the only information about prospects is that they live in the demo location, the information provided about the project would be very general. If the motives are known, appeals can tap onto these motives, identified by the consumer archetypes, by emphasising the corresponding benefits. If the equipment is known, messages can be even more tailored to the benefits obtained by potential participants (e.g., Benefits for EV owners vs. Benefits for PV owners). The last fold foregrounds the number of channels at the disposal of the Demo partner to communicate the messages to the right targets.

The three-fold approach, represented in Figure 12 is explained holistically with potential participants journeys that draw the entire process from a participant perspective based on different scenarios.

Figure 12. Three-fold recruitment strategy approach

4.2.1 Guidelines for targeting or overall approach to recruitment

Targeting stands for the overall approach for recruitment and is the first step and it is key to find eligible consumers. Three requirements determine **eligibility** for participating in ReDREAM's ecosystem:

- **Equipment:** to have at least one of the equipment detailed in **Error! Reference source not found.** or plan to acquire any of them before being recruited to the Demo.
- **Motivation:** willingness to become a user and provide feedback. The reasons can be different depending on the value sought and therefore the consumer archetype.
- **Location:** the building is inside the Demo location area with the capability to provide flexibility to the local grid.

Table 7. Technical requirements by type of user

	Residential	Commercial	Agro-Industrial
Electrical Heating/Cooling	x	x	x
Hot Water with water storage	x	x	x
Swimming pool of more than 15 sqm	x	x	x
Electric vehicles and/or charging posts	x	x	x
Batteries	x	x	x
Big Freezing / Fridges		x	x
Motors or pumps that can be switched off 15 min when they are ON	x	x	x
Other electrical machinery which can be switched off for 15 min without compromising the business		x	x
PV Panels and at least any other of the previous list or PV panels alone if P2P trading is possible	x	x	x

In addition to having the equipment requirements and to being located inside the demo location, potential users need to have the motivation to join the ecosystem. The archetypes identified in Task 1.1. showed that motivation is strongly affected by the perceived ability in dealing with technology-based applications. As reported in Deliverable 1.1., motives vary from obtaining economic value, to be a tractor of the energy transition, to reinforce their identity as tech-savvy or to create value for the community. The initial research unveiled different archetypes of consumers and showed that the prevalence of these archetypes changed across countries. A summary of these findings is shown in Table 8.

Based on our conversations with demo partners in the different workshops and one-to-one meetings and considering their challenges they were facing, two targeting approaches were identified: from motivation to equipment or vice versa. Location, the third criteria for eligibility, should be taken into account in the selection of channel to ensure that messages are only delivered to participants in the appropriate location.

Partners follow a motivation-to-equipment strategy when they target first users with allegedly mid-to-high levels of motivation to join the demo and then later assess their have the right equipment. The opposite strategy implies targeting users that are known to own the equipment and later build their motivation or assess whether they have the motivation to join the project.

Table 8. Archetypes by demo location (summary of key learnings)

DEMO PARTNER	MOST PREVALENT ARCHETYPES	VALUE SOUGHT	MAIN BARRIERS
Croatia	Active Conscious Non-conscious Tech enthusiasts and tech conformists	Reducing bills Convenience Learn and being tech- cool Health-related concerns	Fear of bureaucratic hassle
Italy	Conscious Non-conscious	Reducing bills or other forms of economic value Place attachment (Gallese identity) Protect the environment (especially local)	Avoid hassle, fear of technological artifacts
Spain	Participative Active Tech wary and tech agnostic	Degrowth Reducing bill and other forms of economic value Community/cooperative	Fear of environmental trade-offs, concern about data use and
UK	Participative Active Tech wary and tech agnostic	Reducing bills Greater independence from grid Community value Reduce GHG emissions	Avoid hassle, fear of technological artifacts and concerns about data privacy and data security

4.2.1.1 Motivation-to-Equipment Strategy

The aim of this approach is to find motivated consumers and, among them, identify the ones that meet the equipment requirements. Potential motivated consumers can be divided into different groups, depending on their energy awareness and technological readiness. Depending on their energy awareness, we can distinguish between the non-aware consumers (non-conscious), who are mainly motivated by economic drivers, and the aware consumers (conscious, active and participative), whose main motivators are environmental and/or community, as shown in Figure 13. Depending on their technological readiness, as shown in Figure 14 we differentiate between users with advanced use of technology (tech wary and enthusiast users) and with a medium-low use (tech agnostic and conformist users).

Figure 13. Consumer archetypes based on energy awareness

Figure 14. Consumer archetypes based on their relationship with energy

Approaching these groups starts by understanding where to find those potential participants, be it offline or online. Figure 14 defines potential spaces where some of those consumers can be identified.

Table 9. Spaces for some motivation-segmented target groups

Group	Motivation (value sought)	Offline spaces	Online spaces
Non-aware	Economic	Family-based groups (e.g., schools or local associations) Low-income neighbourhoods	Online fora providing money-saving tips (e.g., blogs or social media channels)
Aware	Environmental or Community value	Consumption Groups Environmental, Community or Local NGOs (e.g., neighbourhood, sustainability, nature protection, etc.) Sustainable or nature-oriented leisure groups (e.g., walking groups) Fair-trade or eco-stores	Local or socio-environmental oriented media (e.g., newspapers, magazines, TV, blogs, radios) Internet fora (e.g., social media, blogs, web sites, chat groups) Sustainable or eco oriented e-commerces (e.g., online supermarkets or marketplace, etc.) Product/service pages (e.g., utilities: green energy, ethical banks or funds, etc.)
Advanced use of technology	Aspirational	Technology stores Cyber-cafes	IoT/smart home internet fora (e.g., social media, blogs, web sites, chat groups) Technology e-commerces IoT/Smart Home product/service pages Followers of a home tech influencer

Then, selecting the right channel and message is critical to attract the attention of potential users in the targeted space. This attention should lead to the expression of an interest in the project. Such expression of interest may be elicited in different forms depending on the channel; to illustrate, click on a banner, ask a question in an online event, or respond to a social media post.

Following the expression of interest, the second step is to verify if users meet the other criteria for eligibility (location and equipment). For this, an eligibility sample form has been developed and will be introduced in section 4.3 (see also Appendix 1. Eligibility form).

Due to the geographical situation of the demos, most of the buildings are heated with gas, and only in Valladolid and Gallese is common to have electric powered cooling systems (these are the only demo locations with summer temperatures over 25° Celsius). Having in a swimming pool is less common, an even so owing electric vehicles or PV panels. Therefore, just a low portion of the motivated consumers that expressed interest will meet the technical requirements to be eligible in the demo locations.

Alternatively, motivated consumers can be encouraged to acquire eligible equipment to meet the technical requirements. The creation of some incentives like financial support, discounts in the product or the services (installation, maintenance, renewal or repairment), the offer of services in exchange etc. could motivate users to acquire the equipment. However, this is costly for users so the benefits should be clearly emphasised.

Motivated consumers can also act as influencers in their local context so to 1. explain the project and extend awareness (in a form of member-get-member promotion) and 2. to encourage others to participate. In particular, market mavens, those consumers that are more energy literate and engage and that enjoy explaining to others how to take part in the energy transition could be targeted in this stage. The field research showed that these motivated consumers took part in digital fora (such as Facebook groups or blogs) as these outlets allowed them to provide advice to others and were members of grassroot movements pushing for the energy transition. Thus, these two platforms could be an appropriate channel to locate and target these influencers.

4.2.1.2 Equipment-to-Motivation Strategy

In this approach, recruitment is first oriented to finding consumers that own flexibility equipment (**Error! Reference source not found.**) or are willing and capable to acquire it. Once they are identified,

those meeting the location and motivation criteria should be selected. Alternatively, motivation can be built so to encourage participate in flexibility provision and efficient energy management with ReDREAM's ecosystem.

To find consumers with eligible equipment, we propose different substrategies (**Figure 15**) to minimise the time and monetary costs; this strategy is more challenging than motivation-to-equipment for two reasons. First, because users with equipment are more difficult to locate. Second, because building motivation is not an easy task: users with eligible equipment (organisations and households) need a focused and dedicated approach to explain the project and persuade them to join (see Guidelines for messages, later), as not all of them will have the motivation to join. It is expected that several contacts will be necessary to convince potential users and demo partners should allocate a bigger budget for this.

Figure 15. Equipment-to-motivation substrategies

- **Strategy A. Business first.** We encourage to start to target consumers with a high possibility of being eligible. It is difficult to know if residential users are eligible or not as there is no public information about the possible equipment they own. However, it is easier to find commercial and agro-industrial users with the right equipment based on the nature of the business they develop. **Error! Reference source not found.** suggest the organisations and industries with a high likelihood of owning the right equipment. Once identified, we advise to conduct an in-person visit to the facility or a cold-call by searching the phone number on the internet and asking for the person in charge of the energy, supplies, or building management. If an e-mail direction is publicly available, this could be also considered as a contact option, although the risk that the email does not reach the adequate person in the firm is greater.

Table 10. Possible commercial and agro-industrial facilities with eligible equipment

Equipment	Commercial	Agro-Industrial
Electrical Heating/Cooling	Gyms, sports centers, Bars/Restaurants, Educational centres (schools, universities, etc.), Residences (students, senior), Offices, Public buildings, Malls,	Industrial firms with cooling or heating as central processes (eg., foundries, plastic injection, ceramic, metal, or stone cutting) Livestock farms
Hot Water with water storage	Health centers/Hospitals, Petrol Stations, Retail shops, Hotels/Holiday retreats	Industrial firms with cooling or heating as central process Food processing facilities
Swimming pool of more than 15 sqm	Gyms, sports centres, educational centers, Hotels/Holiday retreats	Water treating plants, Desalt center, Food processing facilities, Farms,
Electric vehicles and/or charging posts	Public services (police, garbage collection), delivery companies (vans, motorbikes), on-the-site service providers with electrical fleet, etc.	Warehouses, Garbage/Recycling facilities
Batteries	Health centers/Hospitals	Any industrial machinery with batteries and chargers or Any with batteries at big scale
Big Freezing / Fridges	Supermarkets, Fresh Groceries stores, Bars/Restaurants, Pastry shops, Petrol Stations, Hotels/Holiday retreats	Farms, Food processing facilities (winery, brewery, juice, meat, bakery, dairy, fruit & vegetables, fish, canned food, etc.)
Motors or pumps that can be switched off 15 min when they are ON	Gyms or sports centres, Petrol Stations, Hotels/Holiday retreats	Water treating plants, Food processing facilities, Farms
Other electrical machinery which can be switched off for 15 min without compromising the business	Gyms, sports centres, Bars/Restaurants, Educational centres (schools, universities, etc.), Residences (students, senior), Offices, Public buildings, Malls, Health centres/Hospitals, Petrol Stations, Retail shops, Hotels/Holiday retreats	All type of industrial facilities (ceramics, metal, plastic, wood, etc.), Farms, Food processing facilities (milling, cleaning, peeling/cutting, etc.) Use to have mechanical, thermal or chemical storage
PV Panels and at least any other of the previous list or PV panels alone if P2P trading is possible	Gyms, sports centers, Schools, Residences (students, senior), Office's buildings, public buildings, Malls, Health centres/Hospitals, Petrol Stations, Hotels/Holiday retreats	Farms with watering systems, industrial warehouses

- **Strategy B. From burst shooting to sniper.** This strategy consists of finding find a residential consumer with the required equipment and then find others assuming that similar consumers will be in the surroundings.
It should start with a digital marketing campaign (using paid e-mail, or paid Facebook or Google adds) targeting the demo geographical area and considering the other conditions for eligibility options – namely, motivation (consumers with interest in saving money, reducing electricity bill, tech enthusiasts, socio-environmentally aware, etc.) and equipment (with or with interest into EV, PV panels, heat pumps, etc.). These adds should encourage them to fill the eligibility form in order to find a pool of eligible prospects. An analysis of these eligible consumers (address and post? code) may help to identify key patterns that will be later used in a sniper approach for a second marketing campaign,

much more targeted, or a member get member strategic approach (see following proposed strategies). Possible assumptions are described in **Error! Reference source not found.** complimented with a suggestion of next steps and action plan for a targeted campaign.

Table 11. Assumptions and next steps for residential consumer with eligible equipment

Equipment	Assumption	Next steps/Action plan
Electrical Heating/Cooling Hot Water with water storage	If users live in a condominium, other apartments will probably also have electrical heating/cooling as the building will have no gas supply. If they live in a detached house, they can still live in area without gas supply; or it may be a new construction that could be part of bigger housing development with electric heating.	First engage the user and then try a member-get-member approach (Strategy E) for the rest of the neighbours; collect the address as soon as possible to do an in-person visit; introduce leaflets in the post boxes; contact the building doorman or cold-call any of the passing-by neighbours.
Swimming pool of more than 15 sqm	In the Southern Europe demo location, users living in a detached house or in housing development may own a swimming pool.	First engage the user and then try a member-get-member approach (Strategy E) for the rest of the neighbours; collect the address as soon as possible to do an in-person visit; introduce leaflets in the post boxes; contact the building doorman or president or cold-call any of the passing-by neighbours.
Electric vehicles and/or charging posts Batteries	Probably they will know other family, friends, or neighbours with electric vehicle/batteries they have advised or have been advised from.	First engage the user and then try a member-get-member approach (Strategy E)
PV Panels and at least any other of the previous list or PV panels alone if P2P trading is possible	If a person has visible PV panels, other neighbours have them too due to similar roof orientation and because of imitation. Probably they will also know other family, friends with PV panels they have advised or have been advised from.	First engage the user and then try a member-get-member approach (Strategy E) for the rest of the neighbours; collect the address by inspecting the houses and arrange an in-person visit; drop leaflets in the post boxes of other houses with visible PV panels; cold-call passing-by neighbours.

- **Strategy C: Spot the jalopy.** This is a rudimentary but effective strategy to spot equipment that is visible from the outside (PV panels, electrical heating/cooling, EV vehicles or swimming pools. It can be done using a digital tool (e.g., Google Earth) or offline by observing the houses.
Knowing the location of potential eligible consumers could be very helpful to efficiently plan a leaflet-based campaign or to activate local initiatives in the surroundings by using posters, activities, stands, informative vans.

Table 12. Equipment spotting techniques

Equipment	How to spot	Next steps/Action plan
Electrical Heating/Cooling	a) Use public databases with the gas grid to identify areas (buildings, streets, neighbourhoods, or villages without gas supply) b) If you have access to public energy certificates or consumption data (bills, meters, etc.) find users with above average electric consumption; this would suggest electric heating and cooling. c) Use house rental portals (AirBnB, Booking, etc.) with filter options to identify houses in the demo location with electrical heating or A/C.	Create a digital marketing campaign targeting areas without gas supply. Drop leaflets in post boxes and/or cold-call passing-by neighbours. Contact the owner/landlord/hosts.
Swimming pool of more than 15 sqm	a) Use house rental portals (AirBnB, Booking, etc.) with filter options to identify houses in the demo location with swimming pools. b) Use Google Earth to locate swimming pools and extract the addresses.	Arrange an in-person visit; drop leaflets in the post boxes; cold-call passing-by neighbours. Contact the owner/landlord/host if the information is available.
Electric vehicles and/or charging posts	Search for public (street or parking) or semi-public (petrol stations, mall/supermarket parking) charging points in any of the multiple databases accessible online.	Drop a leaflet in the car's windscreen if there is a car charging at the moment. Partner with the organization where the charger is located, to place an informative sticker about the project in the charging point.
PV Panels and at least any other of the previous list or PV panels alone if P2P trading is possible	Use Google Earth to find PV panels installed in roofs and extract the addresses.	Make an in-person visit; drop leaflets in the post boxes; cold-call passing-by neighbours.

- **Strategy D. Member-get-member.** Once you have identified an eligible consumer with the eligibility form, encourage and incentive them to invite other peers that can participate in the project. This is called member-get-member strategy and works specially well with technological pioneers (tech enthusiast) and the archetypes of most active users, who are willing to involve other people. Incentives can be economic or identity-based (e.g., badges), so that they are recognized and singled out in the community as market mavens or green influencers in the community.
- **Strategy E. From installers to ambassadors.** Try to partner with equipment providers or retailers (those doing maintenance, repairing or sell equipment to consumers). They can act as ambassadors of ReDREAM and recommend participation to their consumers. Build a solid incentive plan, both for installers and their consumer, by providing a commission per lead, or by providing a discount on installation. Additionally, installers can be encouraged to use their databases to re-contact users that they have eligible equipment and inform about ReDREAM and offer to participate in the project.

A summary of the targeting approaches is offered in **Error! Reference source not found.** highlights the strengths and weaknesses of the previously developed targeting approaches.

Table 13. Strengths and weaknesses of targeting approaches

	Strengths	Weaknesses
MOTIVATION-TO-EQUIPMENT STRATEGY	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Suitable to use with residential users • Easy to plan digital marketing campaigns • Simple strategy and action plan • Easy to automatise 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low conversion rate from motivated participants to eligible • Higher acquisition costs • Motivation can be diluted if expectations and waiting times are not well managed
EQUIPMENT-TO-MOTIVATION	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Very effective with firms • Shorter spotting and recruitment times • High conversion rates 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High initial effort to spot eligible equipment • Complex strategy and action plan depending on the equipment • Implies manual work and in-person visits • High effort to engage consumers with eligible equipment but not motivated

The decision-making flow chart is a tool that has been developed to help demo partners to choose the right strategy and approach and is furtherly explained in sub-section Decision-making flow chart.

4.2.2 Guidelines for messages

Messages are fundamental to explain the project and build motivation to participate in ReDREAM. Crafting right messages is not an easy task and several problems are pointed out by demo partners. Flexibility is a difficult concept to explain in a short sentence, benefits should be differently explained to different archetypes, and messages should change along the consumer journey. The recommendations below are based on a set of principles to ensure communication effectiveness.

Tell the right story to your target

- When preparing the messages think of the archetypes you are talking to.
- The research done at the beginning of the project unveiled key forms of value sought by organisations and individuals in the corresponding countries. Ensure that your message appeals to at least one form of these values. We have included a summary in **Error! Reference source not found.**
- The research also unveiled key barriers of potential users. Messages should include appeals aimed at minimising these barriers (notably, anticipated stress and fear around data privacy).

Tell the story in the right format

- Use short messages in online environments. Combine with longer texts in landing pages.
- In social media, especially FB, use emoticons to emphasise. Consider adding tags with the main form of value that can resonate to targets.
- Combine texts with pictures and/or videos, to increase open rate and click-through rate. Images would work better if they fit the value sought (economic: money-related images; techno coolness=artifacts; community=pictures of the neighbourhood/local area).

Think of the right message for the right stage in the journey

- When planning for messages, think of the entire journey followed by prospects. The message should be adapted accordingly. For instance, if you include the call to action in a newsletter, you need to plan the message posted in the newsletter, the form that will fill up form, the message they will get when they fill up the form, and the landing pages where they can find more information. They may also go to your FB page to see if there is anything about the project. So, ensure that they can find the information there.
- Websites should be adapted and provide the information that a prospect may seek. You may use the same template as outlined above, and there provide more complete information. If you can include testimonials of participants in past demos that would also encourage participation and build trust.
- Make sure that they can find answers to their questions in these sites. Maybe you can use a FQA section providing clear and short answers to frequent questions: Who is eligible? Why to participate? What's in for you? What's in for your town? What is in for the planet/community? How long does it last? Who pays for the artifacts? How much time does it demand? I am a very busy person, is this suitable for me? Probably, more of these questions are necessary but they can only be identified on the basis of your experience.
- We encourage demo partners to test messages to identify what works best. For instance, different forms of value could be foregrounded and see which messages get more replies. Facebook may be particularly useful to test messages, as it requires low investment (as small as 30 euros), and it may expand visibility and provide greater insights to demo partners.

Either do messages to inform or messages to recruit, but not both in the same message

- When locating prospects, focus on the equipment or the main motivation (trying to cut down your energy bills? Trying to cut down your overall emissions?); when users land on your site, you can explain how the project may help them achieve their goals.
- Include a twofold Call to Action: a call to fill up the eligibility form and a call to spread the word.
- Use positive adjectives to enthusiasm users; avoid plain or factual language.
- Give numbers of how many organisations/households have joined and/or the figure of slots left. Scarcity encourages users to, at least, respond to the form.
- Explain flexibility in a simple way, using examples and focusing on the benefit of flexible grids (economical, environmental, and social) and not on the technical aspects, which are very complex for the user.

You can follow a **template** to prepare the messages as follows

- Who are you talking to: those that...? If you are of those that...
- Why is this interesting for them: benefits for the target; use the value forms or even the verbatims identified in the preliminary research.
- Why is this interesting for their communities: benefits for the community?

- Why is this interesting more broadly: other social and environmental benefits?
- How you can participate: include a call to action to fill up a form
- What the participation entails: provide minimum information to appease stress.
 - Use positive words such as playful, learning, discovery, advance, develop, community growth, comfort, health.
 - Foreground that users have total control over their energy consumption during the project. Refrain from foregrounding “automatisation” at the beginning as this word primes one of the main barriers found among users (lack of control or autonomy).
 - Name the main actors in the project that will create trust among participants: cooperatives and universities. If the project is endorsed by local trusted or well-known figures, use their images. A local high-status figure could be the mayor, a faith-community representative, or the director of the cooperative, if these are the individuals that may create trust. Use pictures of your cooperative if this helps build trust.
 - Encourage individuals to discuss openly the problems or barriers they anticipate. Include a call for “we understand that you may have further questions; we are here for you”.

4.2.3 Guidelines for channels

Examples of channels for locating potential participants are provided in section 4.2.1. Here we expand this initial list with suggestions of other channels.

- It is reasonable to start using owned media, but consider expanding to unpaid media, such as Facebook posts, flyers, or posters in key locations.
- When using exclusively Facebook groups, think if you can reach the whole population with such a single channel. Organisations are not usually followers of such groups, as it is the case of certain social segments.
- Facebook events may help promoting webinars or meetings where the project can be explained. Consider also using neighbourhood social media, such as Next Door.
- Facebook ads may also provide promising results, especially in a motivation-to-equipment strategy, since it allows microtargeting (targeting users on the basis of their specific location, lifestyles, and interests). Since it is a controlled investment (users decide the maximum amount) it may provide good returns.
- Google ads may help identify eligible users, as it allows targeting by search and location.
- Use LinkedIn if this allows you reaching organisations. Alternatively, you can create a database by running web searches and send an invitation email.
- Onboard local media. Local newspapers and local radios may help reach audiences that email, and social media do not reach. They may also be a fundamental partner in awareness raising.
- Do not exclude personal channels. Especially with organisations, it may be proven more effective to visit and explain.

4.3 Analytical and planning tools

To support demo partners on implement the recruitment strategy, a set of analytical and planning tools have been developed based on the needs and challenges that demo partners shared in the dedicated workshops. The proposed tools are designed to operationalise the threefold framework were presented to all partners in a online meeting. Five tools are presented; four are found in in this section; the last one, the detailed eligibility form, is found in Appendix 1. Eligibility form.

4.3.1 Decision-making flow chart

A decision-making flow chart (Figure 16) has been defined to help Demo partners to decide what type of message, content, and channel they could be used depending on the targeting strategy and if the contact information available. This flowchart has as a starting point the willingness to connect with a specific type of person among the universe of potential participants. It can be someone from a specific community the Demo is part of or has relationship with (e.g., association, Facebook Group, data base of consumers or leads, readers of a specialised blog, audience of a local radio channel, etc.). Once the audience is decided, two alongside analyses are required for communication planning.

First, demo partners do have to verify if they have the contact information of this audience and depending on the answer different channels are suggested to reach them. If the Demo partner has the contact info, as for example the e-mail of the person, then the use of direct connections through own unpaid channels is recommended, as those will enable to personalize the content to the archetype and be the most economic option. There are several channels and format suggested for this type of circumstance that can be combined based on the message that will be transmitted. Both online and offline channels are recommended. For example, communicating a key message in a talk (format) in a offline event (channel) could be very effective for people with a strong sense of community, a participative attitude and technological reactance. Using a newsletter via e-mail will help reach the more tech-savvy audience and catch their attention.

If demo partners do not have the contact info, then paid or earned (unpaid) media from third -party actors would be the appropriate contact channels. Although more alternatives and formats are available, compared to the owned media, the effectiveness to reach the right audience will be lower and so will be the conversion rate. To give an example of an earned media channel, being interviewed in a video posted in a sustainable-consumption association explaining the project and benefits and impact of participating, will help to reach the right audience based on the value sought.

Second, the analysis of the expression of interest should show whether the person is eligible or not for the project. If not, they should be nonetheless encouraged to spread the word with a member-get-member type of message. Depending on the approach selected, different guidelines for messages, explained in section 4.2.2 need to be considered.

Figure 16. Target-channel-message decision-making tree

4.3.2 Participants' recruitment journey

User journeys are an excellent tool to understand the real user needs and how would they interact all along the recruitment process. They help to analyse all the possible contact points with potential users, anticipate how the demo partner can seize these contact points and gain access to the potential users. We have drafted two explanatory participants recruiting journeys to illustrate and apply some of the recommendations described above. The first one (Figure 17) depicts an almost entirely digital journey; the second one (Figure 17. Example 1. Participant's recruiting journey) depicts a user mostly engaged with offline channels and interactions.

Three golden rules are recommended to increase engagement and manage prospects' expectations during the recruiting journey.

1. **RECURRENT COMMUNICATION:** do not leave more than 7 days between contacts; without getting in touch with the participants if there is no scheduled next step, like an event or call. This will help "keep the flame alive".
2. **PROVIDE CERTAINTY OF THE PROCESS:** always explain in which step the candidate is at and clarify the next step/s. Consider giving an update of the status of the participation and project so that candidates understand this is alive and others like them are joining. Be transparent with dates and manage expectations if initial schedules change.
3. **COMBINE INDIVIDUAL AND COMMUNAL TOUCHPOINTS:** use individual touchpoints to build confidence, closeness, and trust. Candidates will appreciate being treated as unique persons. Use communal touchpoints with other participants to reinforce the social aspect of the projects, foster fear of missing out and show that the project is alive and there is a social interest in it. Candidates feel more secure and decided to take part if they know that other peers are joining.

Example 1 | Online journey

User archetype: Young worker, tech conformist and conscious with an electric car

Figure 17. Example 1. Participant's recruiting journey

Example 2 | Offline Journey

User archetype: Retired, tech wary and active with a hot water cylinder

Figure 18. Example 2. Participant's recruiting journey

4.3.3 Experiments table

We encourage demo partners to acquire an experimentation mindset to test the recruitment tactics and measure the effectiveness to iterate the approach based on evidence. An experiment table (Figure 19) may help compare the results of the different experiments and gather conclusions. The recommended table is based on the threefold approach depicted in section **Error! Reference source not found.**: (1) target - defined by the scope (a Facebook group) and the possible type of users that are part of it; (2) message content, defined by the type of info needed by the target; and (3) channels. Then some recommended KPIs are included to measure effectiveness. They may comprise impressions, interactions, click-through-rate (CTR) of the call to action (CTA) messages, lead-through-rate (LTR) or conversion rate. These KPIs are often provided by the channel manager (i.e., Facebook Mail Chimp or Google Ads dashboard). If such software are not used for campaign management, then indicators can be calculated based on other inputs of data. **Bear in mind that the website needs tagging to be able to get the information to calculate some of the KPIs.** These KPIs are heavily focused on digital channels, but other KPIs for the offline channels can be considered and calculated similarly (e.g., LTR can be calculated as the number of individuals filling up a form in a face-to-face assembly/total number of individuals attending an assembly).

To illustrate the type of experiments that can be conducted, demo partners may test which combination of target, channel and message works better. This table allows seeing the possibilities related with the target and the touchpoints to use with each user. It is a tool to work on the type of user and the message and channel to use. Also, it facilitates to measure of the main KPIs used on each channel and target so we can understand better if we are reaching positively and iterate if needed.

TARGET	TYPE OF USER	MESSAGE CONTENT	TYPE OF CHANNEL	CHANNEL	SCOPE	% Visibility (Impressions)	% Interactions (Likes, shares, comments over impressions)	% CTR of CTA ^{*Optional}	Prospects Lead Through Rate	% Conversion
FACEBOOK GROUP GALLESSE	LIVE IN THE DEMO LOCATION	BLEND	OWN UNPAID	POST						
EV FACEBOOK GROUP CROATIA	MEET TECH REQUIREMENTS MOTIVATION, WILLINGNESS AND/OR CAPACITY TO PARTICIPATE	EV TECH ECON	PAID	OTHERS SOCIAL MEDIA						
SUSTAINABLE WELLS	MOTIVATION, WILLINGNESS AND/OR CAPACITY TO PARTICIPATE	PV PANNELS TECH ENVIRO ECON SOCIAL	EARNED UNPAID	INSTALLER						
...

Figure 19. Experiment table example of channels

Alternatively, just messages can be tested (A/B testing). You can prepare two FB posts and post them on a similar weekday (both on Tuesday) at a similar time (both at 13.00) and see which one gets more impressions and interactions. If doing this experiment by email, you can send message A to half of your database and message B to the other half and see which message gets more open rates, more leads and lesser bounce rates. This experiment can also be done test channels by using the same message and test it in two different channels (e.g., Facebook vs. Instagram).

4.3.4 Initiative’s matrix

A valuable tool to generate more touchpoints for potential candidates is the initiative matrix (Figure 20). This matrix considers two variables: users with specific technical requirements (Y-axis) and channels (X-axis). The crossing points define the specific initiative or action that can be activated. This is an exercise that serves first as a brainstorming method and second as a framework to visualise all the initiatives in one place. The matrix also helps to visualise the effort taken by each type of users and

channel. We recommend using this matrix for planning communication and recruitment activities, ensuring the entire scope of potential targets is covered.

Figure 20. Initiative's matrix

5 Onboarding strategy

5.1 Introduction

This section focuses on how to ensure engagement while consumers are adopting the new solutions (hardware and software of the ReDREAM's ecosystem) and the new consumption behaviours while onboarded into the ecosystem. This is by far the shortest stage participants will come through during the entire process; notwithstanding, it is a critical stage as conversion occurs in this stage: the intention to participate becomes the initial adoption of the technology solution and the new role demanded from users in the energy transition. During the recruitment stage, potential participants express their interest to participate in ReDREAM and if they are eligible, they are invited to adopt the solution, but they are not offering their resources yet for flexibility. It is in the onboarding stage where participants match their resources into the ecosystem and later will be integrated them. In sum, resource integration leading to value creation starts in this stage.

The main barrier for participants in this stage is perceived stress. As demo partners explained – notably the UK demo partner-, there are some eligible the participants that do not finish the onboarding stage and join the project, due to the perceived hassle in the process. The effort and time required to provide all the information requested by the solution surpasses the value perceived leading to abandonment. This section proposes a strategy to avoid disengagement and to ensure that resources are eventually integrated in the ecosystem and that perceived value is maintained. The strategy aims to ensure a seamless transition stage from intention to service provision, thus avoiding hassle and minimising anticipated anxiety. The strategy is structured based on the users' journey through onboarding (5.2.) and is grounded on the overall ReDREAM design principles (5.3.). Finally, we provide tailored suggestions depending on each demo specificities (5.4.).

5.2 Consumers onboarding journey

The onboarding journey is defined by eight steps that participants will go through. The entire journey should not last more than 15 days so that participants do not lose the momentum once they have been accepted into the project. The eight steps are defined in the two first uses cases presented in the Annex of deliverable D.1.1. The first seven steps refer to use case number 1, *Initial profiling and device installation*, shown in **Error! Reference source not found.** and the last step is detailed in use case number 2, *Onboarding (Smartphone App)*, and refers to the first interactions a user will do with the digital solution when the resources are already integrated in the ecosystem (Figure 21).

ONBOARDING JOURNEY

Figure 21. ReDREAM's onboarding journey

5.3 ReDREAM principles applied to the onboarding process

The five design principles of the ReDREAM ecosystem should also inspire and be reflected in the onboarding process, as discussed next.

5.3.1 Personalisation

Language: every participant should be able to interact with the ecosystem in its language; energy is a complex topic and using a non-native language increases the difficulties and perceived hassle (it is not expected that potential users are familiar with the English terms for devices or parts of the household).

Local representation: interfaces and communications should include images or specific reference to their local organisations. Presently, the recruitment stage is carried out by the demo partners, but the onboarding stage is managed by a different firm. Potential users need to feel that they are dealing with their local organisation to whom they feel attached. Community is one of the three main drivers especially for residential and small businesses and creating attachment since the very beginning increases the motivation and the perceived value. In the following table (**Error! Reference source not found.**), we suggest how local representation could be enabled for each of the demos.

Table 14. Local references to highlight in the onboarding process per demo

CROATIA	ITALY	SPAIN	UK
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • City of Varazdin and Surroundings • ZEZ Community 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Municipality of Gallese • Biodistretto della Via Amerina delle Forre 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energética Cooperativa • City of Valladolid Region of Castilla y Leon 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Constraint Management Zone • Southwest region of Wells • Bath & Surroundings • Avalon & BWCE communities

Energy literacy: onboarding language should be comprehensible for any type of user. We can expect that industrial users are more apt at providing technical information (e.g., specifications of equipment, consumption in kWh, type of power, etc.) and that residential and commercial participants are less apt. So, unless two separate onboarding forms are used, the questions and information requested should be worded in the most plain and understandable terms. Some examples are provided in the following table (**Error! Reference source not found.**). Also, when it is not evident why this information is requested, a short text should clarify why providing the information is fundamental.

Table 15. Adaption of onboarding form to the type of user

INFORMATION NEEDED	QUESTION ADAPTED TO THE TYPE OF USER	
	Residential and Commercial consumers	Agro-industrial consumer
Type of energy supply	Upload a picture of your switch board. <i>We need it to identify the type of energy supply you are using and provide you the best solution.</i>	Select the type of energy supply you have in your building. <i>We need it to provide you the best solution.</i>
Capacity of the battery of the EV	What brand and model are your EV? <i>We need it to identify the capacity of the battery so to make a better calculation of the potential economic and emissions savings.</i>	Which is the capacity of the battery your electric vehicle/s. <i>We need it to estimate the potential savings and emission reductions.</i> [Provide the option of N/A, and if selected, ask the question suggested for residential users.]

Consumer segmentation: during the onboarding process, users should be profiled with a questionnaire based on the consumer archetypes. Thus, we will be able to identify their main value sought, level of awareness and technology adoption, and therefore be able to personalize the interaction of the ecosystem based on their preferences. This will happen in the operation stage with the use of the ecosystem.

5.3.2 Visibility

Manage expectations: during the onboarding is key to always provide certainty to the user of progress achieved and pending tasks and time by highlighting how much has been completed and what remains to be done. This may mitigate anxiety and therefore avoid abandonment. Some solutions that could work is the inclusion of a progress bar and the communication of the time expected for completing each section and for completing the entire onboarding. With these aids, participants can better plan when to fill the onboarding form so to minimise the interrupted forms and churn rate. This is also applicable for messages outside the platform that clarify timings and next steps (e.g., how long it will take to arrange a meeting with the installers, or the expected duration of the installation, or the expected time when the final approval will be communicated to the user).

Reinforce perceived value for users: users will make an effort if they anticipate value. Participants should anticipate value or realise value in every interaction. This implies that for every question or request, the ecosystem should return a value proposition in exchange. Explaining the reason for information request and how the information provided by the user will be used to provide value are fundamental to avoid disengagement. Some examples are provided in **Error! Reference source not found.**, highlighted in italics. It is fundamental to bear in mind that value may adopt many forms, so the onboarding form should explain how the information provided will be the basis for saving money, reducing emissions, or supporting the community. As there is no strong correlation between a driver

and a type of user or location, we recommend including all of them balanced along the different interactions.

Provide an alternative way of providing the information or asking for help: visibility implies that users maintain a clear understanding of what they must do. It is very likely that users may have questions or doubts about the meaning of some of the requirements or their buildings may not fit with the standards on which the onboarding form is based on. Thus, when encountering questions or requests they are unsure about, users may be tempted to abandon the onboarding. To avoid this, it is important to provide a solution that help users go along the onboarding process. This can be translated in providing a N/A answer option, the possibility to complete that question/section later and jump to the next one, or to include an extended information section that provides a more complete explanation or that solves the users' doubts. We also recommend facilitating a contact point to ask (and obtain answers) their questions. It can be a live chat, a phone number, a call scheduling, or a place to leave a message. Of course, real time contact is the best option, as this will minimise the churn rate during the onboarding; however, if not feasible a combination of synchronous and asynchronous help is advised.

Transparency: data privacy is a common concern for all demos and types of users, but especially for residential users. As the initial research (1.1.) showed and as confirmed in the literature review, residential users are reluctant to share personal information that they anticipate as risky. Bear in mind that mistrust is widespread in certain services such as energy or banking. Hence, when highly sensitive information is requested (e.g., the footprint of the house), users should receive a clear explanation as to why this is required and how this information will be treated and managed and by whom. For instance, if the home address is requested, the form should explain that the address is necessary to arrange the installation of the equipment. Users will understand the reason and will see the value on it, as it is going to ease the process. Transparency also reflects in the terms and conditions document. A long document with complex legal and technical language or small size fonts comments at the bottom does not convey transparency nor does it build trust. If these documents should be maintained for legal reasons, then translate them into more user-friendly formats like videos or infographics, using a plain and understandable language for an average user.

5.3.3 Simplicity

Visualisation: energy is complex for users, and to properly integrate consumer resources for flexibility a high level of detail is needed from their energy equipment and installations. Explaining complex requests by using examples, pictures or videos of what is needed is helpful and will help users understand the questions. Also designing interfaces or touchpoints with a strong visual approach can ease users' interaction and reduce the dedicated time. For instance, using appropriately colour to mark differentiate sections or concepts or use consistently icons for equipment or stages. Also, the use of interaction buttons is preferable to asking the user to type text. This should be implemented whenever possible. In sum, users need to have the sensation to overfly onboarding rather than to deep dive, as it is merely a transition phase; we should not deplete users' energy and commitment as this is necessary in the next stage.

Language: language should be simple and colloquial, although adapted to the cultural expectations. Generally, technicisms or specific jargon should be avoided, or when it is unavoidable, then an explanation of the term should be provided in the text or in an information bottom.

Less is more: to avoid hassle in this phase, a thorough revision of the questions absolutely needed is required, to reduce its number. Also, to reduce complexity, bottoms, interactions or messages can be included to aid users. This optimization process will lessen users' anxiety.

5.3.4 Discoverability

Teach the user and create awareness: the main goal of ReDREAM project is to increase the participation of consumers in the energy market. It goes without saying that participation requires a previous understanding of energy services and energy markets. The onboarding process is an

opportunity to explain what flexibility is, what resources are demanded and integrated and what is expected from consumers to make it possible. Providing a short explanation (see **Error! Reference source not found.**) could also reinforce the perceived value and help users understand how the resource integration will enable it.

Dose critical messages along the process: educating users does not imply "infixating" them. It is not necessary to provide a full explanation of all details and process entailed in flexibility services as this would certainly create anxiety among users. This dosage is compatible with maintaining transparency and visibility; the objective is to provide the right information at the right time, so to maintain a balance between the positive emotions associated with learning (pride, excitement) but not that much information that makes users feel overwhelmed. For example, data protection and management or terms and conditions document is an interaction point that could create friction to the user, so we recommend not to bring present it forms the very beginning and relay them to the final steps, but to friendly and simply inform about the data implications from the beginning.

5.3.5 Managed Automation

Prefilled options: to avoid hassle, it would be necessary to provide as much as possible prefilled options to the user so that they can reduce the effort and time by providing the information. This also reduces anxiety produced by the number of empty boxes/forms that they need to fulfil. The prefilled options should be also adapted to the different profiles. For instance, if there is a non-obvious question about the type of rooftop isolation of the house, then the most common or frequent response for residential users in that demo location should be prefilled. As most users fill up the onboarding form, it becomes easier to unveil the mode response and use it to prefill the answers.

5.4 Guidelines for onboarding process

This section summarizes how the design principles should be implemented in the onboarding process, detailing what should be done and by whom (

Step of the journey	Principles	Possible actions
1. Link for ecosystem registration	Visibility	The responsible person of the cooperative/local community, after the recruitment process, sends the participant a link to finish the registration in the ecosystem. The user clicks on the link and accesses the ecosystem web app. S/he finds an introduction to the project and ecosystem that explains (in a video, text, and infographics): Why it is important to have him/her on board What flexibility is (video) What we need from them in the next months How the ecosystem works, both individually and collectively (infographics)
2. Welcome on the ecosystem	Personalisation	Call the user by his/her name and highlight the three types of value provided with the ecosystem according to the value sought by archetypes.
3. Explanation of the questionnaire	Simplicity	Provide instructions regarding the form: questions asked, time requested to completion, reasons for the information requested (connecting value and resource integration).
4. Questions for profiling	Discoverability Simplicity	Users find questions about the building/household, such as: Estimated year of construction Efficiency label Appliances and devices list Households Number of rooms Vehicle and/or garage Each item of information requested is accompanied by a short explanation about why it is necessary and how this information will create value.
5. Approval	Visibility	Provide clear instructions to manage expectations and waiting times.
6. Sign terms and conditions	Simplicity	Do not overwhelm the user with complex legal documents. Try to explain terms and conditions in a simple, short, and understandable manner. Building trust is fundamental so add information about the organization requesting the information.
7. Schedule an appointment for device installation	Personalisation Managed automation	Once all questions have been responded, the user chooses a calendar and marks the most suitable dates for the installation appointment. User provides address, email, and phone number to arrange this visit. After confirming the meeting, s/he receives a confirmation email/SMS as chosen by the users.
8. Installation	Simplicity	The selected day a technician arrives at the house of the participant and installs the devices. Also at this stage, trouble and anxiety should be minimized by assuming all the implications and changes needed and relying as less as possible in the household. Technicians are key to manage expectations around the complexity of the equipment vs the simplicity of the user experience.
9. Onboarding on the ecosystem app	Simplicity Personalisation	A welcome message pops up: "Thank you for joining ReDREAM; to help you be more efficient, we need you to give us some information about you and your consumption so we can personalise your experience in the ReDREAM ecosystem."

Table 16).

Step of the journey	Principles	Possible actions
10. Link for ecosystem registration	Visibility	The responsible person of the cooperative/local community, after the recruitment process, sends the participant a link to finish the registration in the ecosystem. The user clicks on the link and accesses the ecosystem web app. S/he finds an introduction to the project and ecosystem that explains (in a video, text, and infographics): Why it is important to have him/her on board What flexibility is (video) What we need from them in the next months How the ecosystem works, both individually and collectively (infographics)
11. Welcome on the ecosystem	Personalisation	Call the user by his/her name and highlight the three types of value provided with the ecosystem according to the value sought by archetypes.
12. Explanation of the questionnaire	Simplicity	Provide instructions regarding the form: questions asked, time requested to completion, reasons for the information requested (connecting value and resource integration).
13. Questions for profiling	Discoverability Simplicity	Users find questions about the building/household, such as: Estimated year of construction Efficiency label Appliances and devices list Households Number of rooms Vehicle and/or garage Each item of information requested is accompanied by a short explanation about why it is necessary and how this information will create value.
14. Approval	Visibility	Provide clear instructions to manage expectations and waiting times.
15. Sign terms and conditions	Simplicity	Do not overwhelm the user with complex legal documents. Try to explain terms and conditions in a simple, short, and understandable manner. Building trust is fundamental so add information about the organization requesting the information.
16. Schedule an appointment for device installation	Personalisation Managed automation	Once all questions have been responded, the user chooses a calendar and marks the most suitable dates for the installation appointment. User provides address, email, and phone number to arrange this visit. After confirming the meeting, s/he receives a confirmation email/SMS as chosen by the users.
17. Installation	Simplicity	The selected day a technician arrives at the house of the participant and installs the devices. Also at this stage, trouble and anxiety should be minimized by assuming all the implications and changes needed and relying as less as possible in the household. Technicians are key to manage expectations around the complexity of the equipment vs the simplicity of the user experience.
18. Onboarding on the ecosystem app	Simplicity Personalisation	A welcome message pops up: "Thank you for joining ReDREAM; to help you be more efficient, we need you to give us some information about you and your consumption so we can personalise your experience in the ReDREAM ecosystem."

Table 16. Guidelines for the onboarding process.

6 Operation strategy

6.1 Introduction

This section briefly explains how to maintain consumers engaged while they are participating in the ReDREAM project by operating with the ecosystem for flexibility provisioning and efficient management of the energy, which is the main objective of the engagement strategy and of the project, as explained in sub-section 3.1.

Flexibility provision will be enabled by the automatisation mode of the app since the service depends on the intelligent software. Thus, engagement in this stage consists in ensuring the three pillars (3.2), users must trust the ecosystem so that it can manage their resources to automatically provide flexibility when needed; the effort requested from consumers should be compensated with perceived benefits; perceived value and resource integration is sustained in time.

Although flexibility provision is mostly automatised, efficient management of energy is not. Efficient management requires previous knowledge as a condition to make the right decisions. However, energy illiteracy, in different degrees, is the norm among residential and commercial users – insofar as energy is a key resource for agro-industrial users they usually have dedicated staff with energy knowledge or expertise -.

These arguments should be reflected in the strategy for engagement in the participation stage. The design principles must guide the overall approach; notwithstanding, other elements are relevant in this stage, notably specific features that boost and maintain engagement and the human relationships -e.g., support from the local partner, which is the person in charge of solving any trouble or question of participants-. These three elements- design principles, features and human support. will be developed in the following sub-sections. As some of them have been already developed in Deliverable 1.1, here a brief summary is presented.

6.2 ReDREAM's principles and technological musts to ensure participation

As described in sections 4 and 5.3, the ecosystem is guided by five design principles that together ensure that the ecosystem responds to users' needs and desires. The technological musts, mentioned in Deliverable 1.1 and **Error! Reference source not found.**, also ensure that this technological tool fits all consumer archetypes by technology adoption. Technology resistance is one of the main barriers for engagement.

Design principles and technological musts are not only key to understand how the ecosystem design should work to be responsive to user's needs but also should serve as a **guide to guarantee participants engagement all along the journey**. These principles must be "checked" in almost every process of the ecosystem design functionalities, as they are the guardians of the user's motivations and expectations. They are summarized next.

- **Personalisation:** any setting could be able to be adapted to the user's motivation (value sought) and user's preferences. Settings may refer to, *inter alia*, privacy settings, notifications, or details of the info.
- **Visibility:** information must be transparent. This concerns management, justification of its need, destination, and visualization of the user's impact.

- **Simplicity:** less is more; include only what is essential for users. Show other possibilities for curious or advanced users so that they can access deeper information or more complex functionalities.
- **Discoverability:** provide an experience that unfolds in a journey depending on the curiosity, progress, and engagement of the users, while maintaining the educational and empowerment *ethos* of the project.
- **Managed automation:** always bet on the maximum automation possible, but still manage to make users feel and have the control whenever they feel like

Table 17. Ecosystem musts defined by archetype

TECH ENTHUSIAST	TECH WARY	TECH CONFORMIST	TECH AGNOSTIC
Control: automation must give a sense of control. Personalisation: technology must provide everything with a prominent level of personalisation. Depth: information must be concise and yet deep and wide in scope.	Commodity: automation must bring them convenience. Real-time: technology must make them capable to decide in real-time. Ethics: technology must be ethical and have a purpose. Transparency: transparency and data management are crucial.	Practicality: automation must make users' life easier as they are not willing to devote much time or effort. Simplicity: technology must be easy but is considered necessary. Security: technology and devices must help them take care of their data.	Trust: automation must be a tool to make them trust it. Service: technology must be a tool with few interactions. Privacy: technology must make them feel not surveyed or invaded.

6.3 Ecosystem features that foster engagement

As previously mentioned, some of the ecosystem features – namely the advisory tool, dashboard and challenges (Figure 23)-aim at ensuring users' learning. Users should understand how their house/building uses energy in different days/times in order facilitate decision making and behavioural changes towards and efficient management of their energy. In contrast, flexibility provision will run in the back completely automatised.

Figure 22 ReDREAM's ecosystem features and design guidelines.

It is also expected that these three features will not be used by all participants. However, this should not be interpreted as lack of engagement: they will provide flexibility just by integrating their resources (energy equipment) and enabling the automatised mode.

The ecosystem should be responsive to the behavioural signals of the users during interactions. It is necessary to spot signals of disengagement to introduce corrective actions so that they do not stop doing an efficient energy management and maintain the efficiency when they are engaged.

The social KPIs define in an annex of Deliverable 1.1 will help track users' participation and engagement. Based on the ongoing analysis of this information, we will optimize the ecosystem so that it enables users' behavioural change that will ultimately lead to achieving the targets of this project.

6.3.1 Advisory wall

The Advisory wall provides users with simulations in order to help them make energy efficiency or flexibility decisions. It is supported by the notifications, that advise the user in context and led them to the wall. The engagement strategy considers how users react to the notifications and advises and if they change their behaviours. Based on the KPI tracking, the type, frequency, and topic of the notifications can be modified in order to keep the user aware and alert.

6.3.2 Challenges

Challenges comprise the gamified goals proposed to users and created under a "total engagement perspective". These challenges can be individual (e.g., reduce your consumption while doing the ironing by 20%) or collective (e.g., beat the nearby village in energy flexibilization), and cover energy flexibility, efficiency, and non-energy ambits (mobility, health, and comfort). The main goal of the challenges is to shift consumers behaviour towards a better scenario for themselves, the community, and the environment.

Challenges help consumers evolve their consumer profile towards more engaged, empowered, and knowledgeable while simultaneously being responsive to different profiles. Challenges aim to maintain users' engagement, but they differ in the degree of requested commitment (effort and time).

Depending on the profile that dynamically change, different challenges will be proposed. The social network dimension of community-based challenges is another key ingredient for engagement. Monitoring of challenges' accomplishment and, more importantly, of their impact on behavioural change, will be the basis to revise the gamification approach (e.g., type of challenges, time and effort required, etc.) so that, in future exploitation scenarios for the service providers, an evidence-based stock help design gamified approaches that work.

6.3.3 Progressive functionalities releasement

As explained in Deliverable 1.1 in section 6, a progressive deployment of functionalities is advised so that the deployment adapts to initial users' profiles. This strategy responds directly to the discoverability principle, which main goal is to avoid users' overwhelming with complex and manifold functionalities inside the app. The following table (**Error! Reference source not found.**) is a summary of the previously mentioned section and defines the unlocked functionalities in the three stages identified for the using of the ecosystem app (visualisation, improvement, and participation).

Table 18. Unlocking features during the app using stages

Using stage	Description	Unlocked functionalities
Visualisation	This stage aims to make users aware of their starting point or baseline levels of consumption and impact. The app provides the information to make them aware of different functionalities.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dashboard (F1): with the Consumption graphics (F1.1), the Impact visualiation (F1.3) and the Consumption per device (F1.4). - Challenges (F2): they will only have access to individual challenges about energy efficiency and non-energy. - Advisory Wall (F3) - Settings (F4): My Profile (F4.1), except the public profile, Alerts and Notifications (F4.2), Data & Privacy (F4.3), FAQ section (F4.4), except the support forum, and Contact details and channels (F4.5).
Improvement	Users enter this stage when they start progressing from their baseline measures to a more efficient and flexible relationship with energy.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dashboard (F1): Comparison functionalities (F1.2), Virtualization (F1.5). - Challenges (F2): they will have access to individual challenges about flexibility and all the community challenges. - Settings (F4): they will have access to the public profile (F4.1) and the support forum (F4.4).
Participation	Users enter this stage when they start progressing from their baseline measures to a more efficient and flexible relationship with energy.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Dashboard (F1): Self-Generation dashboard (F1.6) - Challenges (F2): they will have the ability to create new community challenges for others to follow. - Settings (F4): they will have a special recognition when they participate in the support forum (F4.4) - The progress in the journey will be linked to the progress in the users' profile evolution (F4.1).

6.3.4 Personalization of the user interface

Based on the consumer segmentation conducted in the questionnaire during the onboarding phase, the ReDREAM user interface will be personalized by showing consumers the most relevant information according to their preferences to maximize engagement while using it. Therefore, a user with an economic motivation will see highlighted economic information, while a user driven by the environmental cause will see its impact (positive or negative) standing out of the rest of the information. But both of them will be able to see all the information. Also depending on the technology readiness, users will be able to access to de different features (**Error! Reference source not found.**)

and levels or information (Figure 22) sooner or later, in order to always provide the best experience according to the consumer archetype.

6.4 Human connection

6.4.1 Consumer support to ensure engagement

It is highly likely that there will be bugs and errors in the performance of the ecosystem, causing minor (e.g., a section of the app is not working) to critical issues (e.g., the water heating system cannot be turned on anyway) for the participant. We have learnt from past pilots that threats to comfort are reasons for disengagement or, worse, for immediate abandonment of the pilot. This would occur because two main pillars would be transgressed: trust is lost and users perceive net losses, as opposed to benefits.

It is fundamental to implement a contingency strategy in the form of excellent and quick consumer support. The person or team in charge should not only have a strong technical knowledge of the tool, but also be local and close the participants to ensure trust during a critical moment. This contingency strategy is based in three main principles:

- a) **React ASAP:** when users' comfort is compromised, time is the enemy. Ideally, there should be a 24/7 support person available, so that users do not get frustrated when having a trouble by waiting to being able to contact only in working hours. Once an incidence is opened by users, it is fundamental to provide an immediate response of reception and reassure users that a solution is being sought.
- b) **Rebuild trust:** once the solution has been provided, it is important to manage expectations and transmit trust so that, despite the hassle caused, users do not give up or abandon the project. It is also likely that users' trust in the ecosystem will be affected. Rebuilding trust can be achieved by listening to the consumer, by being empathetic with their situation and by being positive about the solution.
- c) **Always provide a solution:** rebuilt engagement and trust demands offering a solution to the service failure. In the worst scenario provide a temporary solution until a more definite one is available.

6.4.2 Parallel initiatives and feedback collection

Another way to engage users is by creating periodically touchpoints, whether individually or collectively (this could be especially appealing for active users). These touchpoints can be e-mails, calls or a physical event or meeting. The aim of these touchpoints is to inform, teach, follow up or collect feedback from participants. These initiatives will support participants' engagement beyond technology, mostly tech agnostics or conformist. With these touchpoints trust can also be reinforced. Touchpoints should also be adapted to the users' profile: households with children or households with restricted mobility may not be expected to attend meetings so a call or a message may be more suitable for contacting them.

6.4.3 Role of flex community champions (leaders)

The cosystem allow for horizontal value co-creation among users by means of the public support forum and community. We expect that those consumers with a more participatory profile will respond to the questions of their peers, offer advice to solve easy problems or to use the app more effectively and are able to act as opinion leaders in the community. We thus expect that community champions actively create influence, referral and knowledge value (Verhoef et al., 2010) and actively contribute to educating other users and reinforcing their energy empowerment. This expectation is based past evidence showing that social networks play a key role in diffusing information and raising energy literacy and that leaders play a fundamental role in building strong ties in these networks (Abrahamse and Steg, 2013). Similarly, a meta-analysis of 25 projects in EU showed that advice from expert peers and exchange of experiences with expert peers was particularly useful in raising energy-related knowledge. Moreover, social networks and community champions created consumer confidence, as they are perceived as independent from commercial interests (Heiskanen et al., 2010).

7 Conclusions

Based on a thorough understanding of users' needs together with an analysis of the approach followed by demo partners, we conclude that each project target has different factors that affect users' participation in smart grid projects. Factors such like community approach, value, value exchange, environmental concern, social factors, previous technological experience, energy effectiveness and cost are key for users to experience and engage in flexibility projects. In particular, people with Biospheric values, environmental (climate change) awareness and environmental self-identity are more likely to adopt and engage with smart energy systems.

Every strategy should be reinforced and sustained by pillars that give consistency and a long-term view. Consumer engagement pillars reflect the key drivers of engagement: value over time, benefit vs effort and trust in the ecosystem should sustain the consumer engagement strategy.

Participation in a pilot is a long-term relationship that should survive three stages. Acknowledgement of these stages and understanding the key pain points in each of them will minimise the attrition rate. Recruitment, onboarding and participation should be considered both as separate stages and as parts of a whole relationship in which consumers will live an entire experience around energy and flexibility. Each phase should be awarded the same importance as the next one.

Targeting stands for the overall approach for recruitment. It is the first step and the first pain point for demo partners. It is fundamental to understand that either equipment, motivation and location will make our three-item equation to target users and ensure efficiency in messages and communication efforts. Motivation is undoubtedly key; however, targeting motivated people with no equipment could lead to frustration as it is harder to access equipment than building motivation. Conversely, users with equipment may be more easily persuaded as we can show that they may gain for their participation in the project. Location also plays a key role, insofar as a limited targeting area reduces possible participants and blocks either motivation or equipment strategies. We have provided avenues for recruitment in order to facilitate spotting users with appropriate equipment.

All the interactions in the ecosystem should be guided by the design principles. Principles are key and should be always considered from beginning to the end, but their application in the onboarding journey is fundamental to not let escape users in this key moment. This is why personalisation in communication and experience, to manage expectations and reinforce the perceived value, to provide alternative ways of getting personal information, transparency, make things visually and simple for users, and make them discover things during the process is key to establish a good relationship from the beginning with users.

As developed in Deliverable 1.1, the ecosystem features are the materialisation and the domain where resource integration will occur. Non-energy services embedded in this tool will be a vehicle to boost engagement by providing extra value for users.

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9 Appendix 1. Eligibility form

This section presents an eligibility form that will serve as the first filtering for candidates, whether they come from an online or offline channel. This form can be quickly filled up by any candidate using any device. Motivation has not been included because this will be tested in further steps once the potential participant has submitted the personal data/contacted the local responsible person and starts engaging in the onboarding journey. Non-motivated candidates will spontaneously exit the process due to self-selection.

We also suggest that the ReDREAM website replaces the snippet "Contact us for more info" with the [eligibility form](#) so that partners can create a database of interested users. It should be fundamental that Demo partners receive this information by redirecting e-mails.

As mentioned in 4.2 Guidelines for targeting messages, the link to the eligibility form should be added to every message or touchpoint in digital channels.

In the following figures, the eligibility form is visually explained with the example of the Demo site in Italy, Gallese. We encourage all Demo partners to adapt and translate the eligibility form to their local context and Demo particularities.

Figure 23. Welcoming screen

The welcoming screen includes all the value sought forms: economical, environmental, and community, reinforcing the local aspect by including a picture of the Demo location. This enhances trust and takes advantage of place attachment. It is a general message as any consumer archetype could arrive in this form any channel and message.

2 → What type of user are you?

- A RESIDENTIAL
- B COMMERCIAL
- C INDUSTRIAL OR FARMING

0 of 6 answered Powered by Typeform

Figure 24. Type of user

Depending on the type of user, different questions related to the technical requirements will be asked. This will also help Demo partners to know how to approach those participants, depending on their needs.

All users will be asked their place of residence or operations, as being inside the Demo site is a mandatory factor to be part of ReDREAM. Demo partners should adjust the answers to their geographical requirements.

3 → Where do you live?

- A Gallese
- B Less that 10km far away from Gallese
- C Other

2 of 3 answered Powered by Typeform

Figure 25. Location

4 → Do you have any of this equipment?

Choose as many as you like

- A Electrical Heating/Cooling
- B Electrical Hot Water with water storage
- C Swimming pool of more than 15 sqm
- D PV Pannels
- E Batteries
- F Electric vehicle
- G Big Freezing / Fridges (not regular)
- H None of the above

3 of 7 answered Powered by Typeform

Figure 26. Technical requirements

Candidates will be asked about their equipment, and if they meet at least one of the requirements, they will be considered eligible for the Demo.

5 → 🏠 Are you planning to buy any of the following?

Choose as many as you like

- A Heat pump
- B PV Pannels
- C Electric vehicle
- D Hot water cylinder
- Key E None

4 of 8 answered Powered by Typeform

Figure 27. Possible equipment acquisition

If candidates do not meet any of the requirements, they will be asked if they have plans to acquire any of them in the following months, as this will consider them as potential participants.

🎉 Congratulations! You are a potential ReDream user.

Please, leave us your contact info so that we can contact you for the next steps.

press Enter ↵

0 of 6 answered Powered by Typeform

Figure 28. Eligibility confirmation

When candidates meet location and technical requirements, they will be congratulated to stimulate their motivation and asked to provide their info to be contacted in the following days.

Figure 29. Denial of eligibility

When candidates are not eligible, they will be informed and asked to share the project with other people they believe could be interested. **They are also provided with a short text to make it easier to share the call.** Therefore, they are opening new possibilities for other candidates. Also, they will be led to the website so that they can know more about the project and the energy challenges.

Figure 30. Local contact person

Before people provide their contact info, the picture and name of the local coordinator person will be shown. Prospects are explained that s/he will be the person that will reach out to the potential participant. If anyone does not want to provide their contact info, they are given the possibility to proactively contact the local coordinator, as their contact information is provided.

The figure displays three sequential screenshots of a Typeform survey. The first screenshot shows a question titled '4 → Name and Surname *' with a mandatory asterisk. Below the title is a short paragraph explaining that personal data will be used for contact and managed under GDPR, with a link to the privacy policy. A text input field contains the placeholder 'Type your answer here...'. The second screenshot shows a question titled '5 → Your best e-mail address *' with a mandatory asterisk. The text input field contains 'name@example.com'. The third screenshot shows a question titled '6 → Phone number' with a sub-label 'Only if you want'. The text input field includes a country code dropdown set to Italy and the number '312 345 6789'. Each screenshot includes a 'Powered by Typeform' logo and a '0 of 6 answered' progress indicator.

Figure 31. Personal info

Eligible candidates or prospects will be asked to provide their personal info. Just name, surname and e-mail will be mandatory, and the option to provide a phone number will be offered for those who prefer to be contacted through this channel. A short message will explain that their data are managed under the GDPR without providing more info to not overwhelm or frighten users. The eligibility form is developed in Typeform that enables three key aspects for the task of filtering candidates:

- **Logic:** you can configure the questions and messages to follow a certain logic (Figure 32) that meets the Demo requirements based on the candidates' answers.

Figure 32. ReDREAM eligibility form logic flow chart

- Source tracking:** Typeform allows UTB tracking, which lets you understand what drives traffic to the eligibility form by adding information to your URL. UTM is a code snippet in your Typeform URL that shows you the source of your responders. The parameters you can track are the source, medium, campaign, term, and content. For example, you can use `&utm_source=facebook` to track your responses coming from Facebook. It also allows for tracking the medium, the campaign, the term, and the content, apart from the source. This feature allows for tracking which messages, channels and/or campaigns are working better.
- Integrations:** you can store the answers in multiple options like Google Sheets or Excel spreadsheets or even connect it to your Google Analytics account.
- Visual customisation** is key to creating engaging and appealing touchpoints, and Typeform allows embedding pictures and videos and customises the visual identity to match ReDREAM's visual identity.

